

PARENTS' INVOLVEMENT IN THE MTB-MLE READING INTERVENTION PROGRAM OF GRADE ONE LEARNERS IN THE DIVISION OF QUEZON

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 5

Pages: 621-653

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1884

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11483850

Manuscript Accepted: 05-10-2024

Parents' Involvement in the MTB-MLE Reading Intervention Program of Grade One Learners in the Division of Quezon

Venuz E. Ogalisco*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Using a descriptive research method, the study examined parental involvement in the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) Reading Intervention Program for Grade One learners in the Division of Quezon. Data were collected through a questionnaire from 370 participants, treated and analyzed using statistical tools including percentage, mean, Kruskal Wallis H-Test, and Dunn Test. Results showed that most of the respondents were aged 31-40, predominantly female, held regular job positions, were college graduates, earned 15,000 pesos or less, had 3 to 4 family members, and were active members of the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA). Moreover, findings revealed that parents actively participated in the reading intervention program, focusing on teaching their children letter sounds and words for Oral Language Development. It was also evident that the parents participated during the program's implementation and post-implementation stages. Challenges faced by parents included limited instructional materials both at schools and at home. While there were no significant differences in parental involvement assessments based on most demographic profiles, occupation, and educational attainment showed notable distinctions. Recommendations include fostering collaboration with parents for reading skill development, continuous monitoring and evaluation of program implementation, providing training and lectures to enhance parental involvement in home-based reading activities, and enhancing intervention programs, and consultation with parents to ensure their participation. Lastly, further research is recommended using upgraded intervention programs coming from the monitoring and evaluation of the existing program while utilizing different population and location.

Keywords: *mother tongue-based multilingual education, oral language development, parental involvement, reading intervention program*

Introduction

Globally, several studies affecting parents' participation in reading produced an equally viable result. A cohort of research from the mid-1960s produced cumulative effects on parents' participation regarding their children's reading performance at home (Bean, Southworth, Keebler, & Fotta, 2020). Some research recommended that parental involvement is required in substantive children's reading with their children's experience, which is significant and needs extensive enhancement in reading. Updated National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) results from 1992 show that learners who gained reading literacy within their families posited higher reading performance than learners with poor reading literacy. Parent involvement was critical to children's growth and development, particularly in the early grades. Early intervention in the child's reading ability predicted good academic performance.

In Asian contexts, it is widely recognized that elementary grades are critical to students' current and future reading achievement. Initial intervention has been shown to be effective in helping children who have trouble reading. Two crucial factors in harnessing early mastery in reading are word recognition and fluency. Also, several approaches in enhancing word recognition and fluency to young learners are made available (Lewis, 2020). Fluency, research says that accompanying and preemptive instructional methodologies with an end view of enhancing the word recognition and fluency of the primary grade learners posit incredible potential in helping the primary learners become advanced readers. Needed support to help readers are determined by the researchers, how to present such support, and when the support is most efficient. The rhetorical question is: how this support can be given when the school curriculum is very full? One answer given by the researchers is that it is at home (George, 2019).

A relevant impact on children's education has an enormous potential towards parents' participation. Several research impacted the academic performance of learners which connoted the significant role of the parents in learners' academic achievement (Henderson, 2018). As stated by Henderson, parents' participation pointed to enhancements in academic achievement, grades, tests scores, and overall academic performance. Also, the study revealed that parents' participation has a significant effect on enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency when it comes to school performance in the school area and by the teachers affecting the integrity, respect, and behavior of the children's family and the teachers. Reading is viewed as a cooperative activity that fosters readers' acquisition of new concepts and ideas to develop their creative faculties in the Philippines. The value of reading and understanding is highlighted in the education field. Several research have been conducted to increase reading performance; yet some skilled students struggle with reading and comprehension. Teachers, therefore, play a critical role in assisting their students to get the most out of reading and become proficient readers. They need significant reading correction and assistance (Cabbuag, 2020).

The DepEd released standard reading assessment tools and programs based on the local situation, such as the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil IRI), Every Child A Reader Program (ECARP), and many more. As posted by the DepEd (2018) in the First District of Quezon, it showed that falling under the instructional level, the reading performance posted rating of 47.99% of the pupils,

falling under frustration level was 35.93% reading performance, and under independent level was 16.08% of the reading performance. According to the findings, some students learned fundamental reading abilities. However, there are still some who demonstrate weak reading skills. In improving pupils' reading performance, different strategies and interventions were made by the teachers. Despite all preparations in minimizing reading problems, some pupils posted a poor reading performance. The teacher views these issues as concerning. In response to this issue, teachers use other methods and tools to reduce the number of slow readers. The problem is solved by conducting reading remediation and practices. (Cabbuag, 2020).

This study aimed to address the issue of low parental involvement in school activities, which can negatively impact students' educational outcomes. By implementing interventions to stimulate parental participation, with a target of achieving at least a 75% participation rate, the study sought to improve the school environment and student success. Focusing on a reading intervention for Grade One learners, the study aimed to attract parents' interest and engagement in school affairs, recognizing the importance of aligning interventions with parental priorities. Overall, the study aimed to create a more collaborative and supportive school environment that benefits both students and the wider school community.

Research Questions

The study focused on determining parents' involvement in the MTB-MLE Reading Intervention Program of Grade One Learners in the Division of Quezon. Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. occupation;
 - 1.4. educational attainment;
 - 1.5. monthly family income;
 - 1.6. family size; and
 - 1.7. parental engagement?
2. What is the level of parents' involvement in the development of their children's reading skills in terms of the following?
 - 2.1. oral language development;
 - 2.2. phonological awareness;
 - 2.3. phonics and word recognition;
 - 2.4. vocabulary development;
 - 2.5. fluency; and
 - 2.6. comprehension?
3. What is the level of involvement in the program's stages of implementation:
 - 3.1. during implementation; and
 - 3.2. post-implementation?
4. Is there any significant difference in the level of the parents' participation in the development of their child's reading skills when the parents are grouped according to profile?
5. Is there any significant difference in the level of the parents' participation in the program's stages of implementation when they are grouped according to profile?
6. What problems do parents encounter in their participation in the program?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive technique. Descriptive survey research supplies the study with relevant and accurate data. A time-saving research strategy, descriptive survey design engages the individuals at the heart of the study goal (Cantrell, 2021). For the study, the descriptive technique was employed to highlight observable traits, patterns, trends, and case analytics. It stated the study's status and condition, as well as how the researcher intends to employ such a method or study. Typically, descriptive research takes a quantitative approach. It can entail compiling quantitative data in computing form that can be tabulated or tallied along a scale, such as test results or the frequency with which a user chooses to use a specific multimedia program feature. Alternatively, it might define data categories like gender or interaction behaviors when using technology in a group context. In descriptive research, information about events is obtained, and the data is organized, tallied, illustrated, and discussed.

This is deemed suitable since the study evaluated the Parents' Level involvement in the Division of Quezon's Grade One Learners Reading Program. The information required for the study was gathered using a questionnaire.

Respondents

The study's population consisted of the parents of Grade One learners in the Division of Quezon. They were the ones from whom the researcher sought information or responses based on their involvement in the reading intervention for Grade One Learners in the

Division of Quezon. The sample size was calculated using the Cochran Sample Size Calculator. This was shown in the following table:

Table 1. *Population and Sample Size of Respondents*

<i>Municipality</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample Size</i>
Burdeos	547	20
Gen Nakar	830	31
Infanta	1609	59
Lucban	963	36
Mauban	1641	60
Pagbilao	1695	62
Panukulan	417	15
Patnanungan	413	15
Jomalig	184	7
Polilio	685	25
Real	832	31
Sampaloc	236	9
Total	10052	370

The basic random sample method was applied in the investigation. "Simple random sampling" is a type of probability sampling in which the researcher selects individuals at random from a population. Each person in the population had an equal chance of being chosen. Next, data was collected from the largest proportion of this arbitrary subset (Calderon, 2019). Create an alphabetized list of every parent of a grade one student in each district, along with the email address that corresponds to each parent. Create a lotto number that is sufficient for each district. Next, choose numbers at random that match the sample size. A respondent is identified by the name of the respondent that corresponds to a certain number. Burdeos, for instance, lots numbered 1 through 547 were prepared. Then twenty numbers from the lots, one for each of the 20 responses were selected. The Google link to the selected respondents were provided to those with their names and email addresses. A different number was chosen from the remaining lots to take the place of the selected respondent, should they choose not to participate.

Instruments

The questionnaire served as the study's primary data collection technique. This was separated into three parts. The first portion determined the respondents' profile. The second section discussed the level of parental involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One Learners in the Division of Quezon. The third section determined the parents' involvement in the stages of implementation. The concluding section discussed the issues faced in the reading intervention program.

The Questionnaire underwent content, concurrent and construct validation. Under content validation, experts help was sought to validate the questionnaire composing of three Educational Program Supervisor specialist in reading both English and Filipino. Based on concurrent and construct validation, the researcher pilot evaluated the instrument was distributed to at least thirty-seven (37) respondents who did not participate in the actual data collection stage. Here, the Cronbach Alpha was calculated. With a Cronbach Alpha of 0.88, the questions posed to the respondents were deemed internally consistent. This indicates that the elements are consistent with each other.

Procedure

The researcher initially requested approval from the research adviser. A draft of the manuscript was developed and submitted together with the questionnaire. The research adviser provided suggestions or modifications for the work. He/she was the one to schedule for proposal defense. After the defense, the instrument was validated and used. After then, a letter requesting authorization to conduct the research was written and sent together with the schedule for the preliminary and final defenses. Through personal distribution or the use of a Google Form, the researcher made the questionnaire available to the intended responders. Data extraction came next. The study's data was tallied and calculated in Microsoft Excel.

Data Analysis

The study utilized the following statistical formula:

Percentage. This assessed the characteristics of the participants in the study's conduct, the respondents.

Mean. Meas was used to measure and compute the responses regarding parental involvement in the reading intervention program of the Grade One learners and the problems met by the parents.

Mann Whitney U-Test. The Mann Whitney U-Test was used to ascertain the significant difference because the study included Likert Type questions.

Kruskal Wallis H-Test. Since the study used Likert type questions, the Kruskal Wallis H-Test was employed to ascertain whether there was a significant difference.

Dunn Test. To determine the location of the significant variances, the Dunn Test was used.

Results and Discussion

The information acquired for statistical analysis is presented in this section. This is broken up into four sections. In the first section, the respondent profile was thoroughly discussed. The second section discusses the level of parental involvement in the Quezon Division's Grade One reading intervention program. The last section discussed the respondents' challenges in taking part in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners in the Quezon Division. The last section assesses whether there has been a significant variation in the level of parental involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners in the Quezon Division, grouped by profile.

1. Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Sex, Occupation, Educational Attainment, Monthly Family Income, Family Size, and Parental Engagement

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
31-40	190	51.4
21-30	94	25.4
41-50	64	17.3
51-60	11	3.0
20 and below	8	2.2
61 and above	3	0.8
Total	370	100.0

Table 2 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents in terms of age. The age group of 31–40 years old made up most respondents, with a frequency of 190 (51.40%). The frequency of 94, or 25.40%, was obtained by those between the ages of 21 and 30. The frequency of 64, or 17.30%, was recorded for those aged 41 to 50. The frequency among those between the ages of 51 and 60 was 11, or 3.00%. The frequency of 8 was acquired by those under 20 years old, with a ratio of 2.20%. Three of the respondents were older than 61.

Likewise, the relationship between a child's age and their capacity to do schoolwork is a matter for the school (Gullo & Burton, 2022). The kids' vested incentive in using their delaying or expediting strategies to get to school is a contentious issue (Jones & Mandeville, 2020). Despite the efforts of educators and psychologists to understand this aspect and its ramifications in the classroom, these themes remain highly debated worldwide. As an example, some argue for regulatory regulations pertaining to kindergarten entry age cut-offs (Jones & Mandeville, 2020).

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>
Female	322	87.0
Male	48	13.0
Total	370	100.0

Table 3 depicts the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by sex. Female replies were the most common, accounting for 322 (87.00%). The remaining respondents were male, with a ratio of 13.00%.

This result indicates that the relationship between the sex of parents and their involvement in reading interventions for their children is complex and influenced by various factors. Historically, societal norms and gender roles have led to mothers being primarily responsible for childcare and education, which may result in higher participation in reading interventions (Wang & Cheung, 2023). However, modern society is witnessing a shift towards more equitable parenting responsibilities, with fathers being encouraged to actively engage in their children's education, including participating in reading interventions (Lanlord, 2021). This reflects broader societal changes towards more equal parenting roles.

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Occupation*

<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Regular	137	37.0
Probationary	112	30.3
Housewife	66	17.8
Others	35	9.5
None	20	5.4
Total	370	100.0

Table 4 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on their occupation. Most respondents were in their Regular Positions in their job with a frequency of 137 (37.00%). Those in the Probationary positions registered a frequency of 112 with a percentage of 30.30%. Housewives got the frequency of 66 with an equivalent percent of 17.80%. Other occupations gained the frequency of 35 (9.50%). Twenty respondents have no occupation.

In the same manner, occupation of parents affects students' performance in their academics (Omalde, Kassim, & Modupe, 2014; Odoh, Ugwuanyi, Odigbo & Chukwujekwu, 2017). But parents' occupation has adverse impact of the academic motivation of learner's success. Students from parents with high occupation level performed poorly compared to those students from parents low and middle occupation level of parents (Walter, 2018). Parents have informal jobs who are self-employed with job without a guarantee to turnover cannot afford to spend a great deal of time on their children (Usaini & Abubukar, 2015). Highly educated parents with high or low occupation level had better outcomes compared to their peers whose parents had low educational and occupation level (Gulada, Chillon, Ruiz & Pavon, 2021).

This study confirms parents' effect on their children's glycemic control. It is found positive connection between educational and occupational levels of father and mother (Aigha, Majdi, Aljefri, Ali, Alagha, Elhamed & El-denwi, 2017). The family socio-economic status of parent's state the father's education, occupation and income affects children's performance (Das & Sinha, 2017). Parents occupation identify the parent's ability to finance the academic performance also (Gabriel, Muli, Muasya, Moanga & Mukhunguku, 2016).

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
College	200	54.1
High School	113	30.5
Vocational	33	8.9
Post-Graduate	17	4.6
Elementary	7	1.9
Total	370	100.0

Table 5 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to educational attainment. Most respondents were college graduates, with a frequency of 200. High school graduates had a frequency of 113, or an equivalent percentage of 30.50%. There were 33 vocational graduates, for a rate of 8.90%. Post-graduates increased their frequency by 17 (4.60%). Seven responders were elementary school graduates.

Davis-Kean, Tighe, and Waters (2020) highlight that parent educational attainment indirectly contributes to children's academic success through parental beliefs, expectations, and cognitive stimulation. Similarly, Geske and Ozola (2020) found a positive correlation between parents' education level and their engagement in reading promotion activities, emphasizing the diverse impact of parental education on children's reading achievement.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Monthly Household Income

<i>Income (in Pesos)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
15,000 and below	181	48.9
15,001 to 30,000	119	32.2
30,001 to 45,000	33	8.9
60,001 and above	22	5.9
45,001 to 60,000	15	4.1
Total	370	100.0

Based on monthly household income, Table 6 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents. 181 (48.90%) of the respondents said they made 15,000 or less annually. Those earning 15,001 to 30,000 had the frequency of 119, or 32.20%. The bracket of 30,001 to 45,000 got the frequency of 33 (8.90%). Those who earned 60,001 and above gained the frequency of 22 (5.90%). Fifteen respondents earned 45,001 to 60,000.

This is consistent with the reality that low-income parents work in average-income jobs, allowing for autonomous decision-making. Given authority, initiative, and creative thought, this type of working environment has a significant impact on parental values and social relationships (Greenberger & O'Neil, 2021; Kohn, 2017).

According to Eccles and Harold's (2013) findings, family income can impact parents' involvement in reading programs for their children in several ways. Lower-income families often face time constraints due to multiple jobs or long working hours, limiting their availability for participation. Additionally, they may lack access to resources like books and technology, hindering their engagement in reading activities. Parents with higher incomes tend to have better educational backgrounds, making them more aware of the importance of reading and better equipped to support their children's literacy. Moreover, transportation and logistical challenges may further impede participation for lower-income families, while differing perceptions of the importance of education may also influence involvement. Addressing these barriers is crucial to ensuring equitable access to literacy support for all children, regardless of family income.

Based on family size, Table 7 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the responses. Most respondents have three to four family members, with a frequency of 204 (55.10%). The following were those with family members of 5 to 6 gaining a frequency of 127 (34.30%). Those with 1 to 2 members had the frequency of 18, or 4.90%. Those 7 to 8 members registered a frequency of 15 with a percentage of 4.10%. The 11-12-member bracket received a frequency of 4, or 1.10%, in comparable terms. 9 or 10 people made up the families of two respondents.

Table 7. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Family Size*

Family Size	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 to 2	18	4.9
3 to 4	204	55.1
5 to 6	127	34.3
7 to 8	15	4.1
9 to 10	2	0.5
11 to 12	4	1.1
Total	370	100.0

This meant that the respondents adhere to the family planning principle of having only three to four people in their family. This could indicate that the populace in the area is under control and within reach of their income earnings. Another study by Nierva (2019) examined the impact of family factors on parental participation. Factors to consider include parents' highest level of education, work status, family size, and family structure. The factors influencing parents who engage in their children's academic progress—both active and passive—were compared. Only first-graders at Siena College in Quezon City are included in the study. It showed that parental participation was significantly influenced by traits relating to the family.

According to Musengaman (2023), family size can impact parents' involvement in reading programs for their children in several ways. Larger families may face greater time constraints as parents must divide their attention and resources among multiple children. This can limit the amount of time parents can dedicate to participating in reading activities with each child individually.

Additionally, Brown, Manning, & Stykes (2015) revealed that larger families may have more diverse needs and schedules, making it challenging to coordinate participation in reading programs. However, some research suggests that larger families may foster a culture of shared learning and collaboration, where older siblings may play a role in supporting younger siblings' literacy development. Ultimately, the impact of family size on parents' involvement in reading programs may vary depending on factors such as parental resources, organization, and the dynamics of individual family relationships.

Table 8. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents in terms of Parental Engagement*

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage (%)
PTA	270	72.97
Home Visitation	72	19.46
Others	25	6.76
None	3	0.81
Total	370	100.00

The frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' parental engagement is displayed in Table 8. Most respondents (72.97%) participated in PTA, with a frequency of 270. Those engaged in Home Visitation got the frequency of 72 (19.46%). Other parental engagements gained the frequency of 25 or 6.76%. Three respondents have no parental engagement.

Several elements were identified as generating adequate interest in parents' involvement in their children's education (Obeidat & Al-Hassan, 2019; Christenson & Sheridan, 2021). According to these studies, the problems have a substantial impact on the development of home-based schooling. The challenges identified included misconceptions about teachers and parents' roles in supporting their children's education (Glasgow & Whitney, 2019), time and financial constraints (Christenson & Sheridan, 2021), and parental qualities and experiences (Eccles & Harold, 2013).

According to Glasgow and Whitney (2019), parents and teachers communicate with each other to persuade parents to participate. The misunderstanding is directed at non-responsive parents. The teachers assume that parents are uninterested in the education of their children. On the other hand, parents believe that teachers restrict their ability to engage in their children's education. Certain parents and instructors believe that certain students do not respect or accept parental engagement, which exacerbates the issue.

2. Level of Parents' Involvement in the Development of their Children's Reading Skills in terms of Oral Language, Phonological Awareness, Phonics and Word Recognition, Vocabulary, Fluency and Comprehension

Table 9 displays the respondent's assessment of the parent's involvement in their children's reading skills development in terms of oral language. The grand mean was 4.27, with a verbal description of "participated," indicating that parents participated in their children's reading development.

The statement "the respondents teach their child the different sounds of the letters in the alphabet and words" garnered the most response, with a mean score of 4.39. It demonstrated the importance of parental participation in teaching their child the fundamentals of language. Parents are the ones who understand their child's capacities to learn from school and discover new things.

Similarly, according to Lareau and Shumar (2016), parental involvement often reinforces unequal power dynamics in educational policies, with parents typically excluded from both the design and implementation of their children's educational experiences. Further studies by Noguera (2021) indicate that school officials often assume that families with low incomes are disinterested in their children's education, attributing academic struggles solely to parental instability and holding parents accountable for their child's academic

difficulties.

Table 9. *Parents' Involvement in the Development of their Children's Reading Skills in terms of Oral Language*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I teach my child vowels and consonants. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng patinig at katinig).	4.29	Participated
I teach my child rhyming of words and words recognition. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng mga tunog ng salita at pagkilala sa salita.)	4.29	Participated
I teach my child the different sounds of the letters in the alphabet and words. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng iba't ibang tunog ng mga titik sa alpabeto at salita.)	4.39	Participated
I teach my child homonyms or letters/words of the same sounds. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng homonyms o mga titik o salita na may parehong tunog o bigkas.)	4.24	Participated
I teach my child the word structure. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng istraktura ng salita.)	4.16	Participated
Grand Mean	4.27	Participated

Legend: "Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)", "Participated (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)"

The following indicators revealed that "the respondents teach their child the vowels and consonants" and "the respondents teach their child rhyming of words and word recognition" have the same mean of 4.29. Teaching their child about vowels and consonants, as well as word rhyming and word identification, incorporates parental empowerment to enhance the morale of both the child and parent. This requires parental involvement in their child's learning ability.

Barton et al. (2014) presented the concept of ecology for involvement by parents, which expands on the conceptualization of parental involvement by envisioning parents are both writers and administrators of the school, alongside their children. With a mean score of 4.16, the lowest possible response stated that "the respondents teach their child the word structure". This refers to children's early literacy development.

Regarding this, Tabbada-Rungduin et al., (2014) explored the role of parents and teachers in children's early literacy development. Findings indicate that parents practice aspects of parental involvement but extreme poverty influences their views on how they support children's education. It pointed out that parental involvement reflects parents' cultural and socioeconomic context.

Table 10 illustrates respondents' perspectives on parental involvement in enhancing their children's phonological awareness and reading skills. The average score of 4.19 for the term "participated" suggests active parental support in children's reading development. The highest-rated item, with a mean score of 4.30, indicates that respondents teach their children rhymes to aid in reading and spelling development, reflecting the role of parental assistance in fostering literacy within the school culture. Ultimately, the goal of reading intervention is to meet children's needs and facilitate their literacy growth to prepare them for active participation in society. Teachers play a constructive role by modeling effective literacy instruction, fostering a culture of literacy among students (Tovani, 2014). Strengthening interpersonal and literary connections can enhance students' comprehension, reading, and writing skills, contributing to a multi-literate approach to education (Akey, 2017).

Table 10. *Parents' Involvement in the Development of their Children's Reading Skills in terms of Phonological Awareness Development*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I teach my child rhythm, rhyme, sounds, and syllables. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng ritmo, tunog at pantig.)	4.21	Participated
I teach my child rhyme in the development of reading and spelling. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng tunog sa pagbuo ng pagbasa at pagbabaybay.)	4.30	Participated
I teach my child to detect and focus on the distinct sounds in words. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng pagkilala at pagpokus ng magkahiwalay na tunog ng salita.)	4.18	Participated
I teach my child to learn to syllabicate words distinct sounds and manipulate them to build novel words. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng paghahati ng pantig sa magkahiwalay na tunog at makabuo ng iba't ibang salita.)	4.19	Participated
I teach my child from here, letter-sound correspondences that can be taught concurrently as phonemes and phonics abilities. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng pagkakaugnay ng titik at tunog na maaaring ituro bilang ponema at ponetikong kakayahan.)	4.08	Participated
Grand Mean	4.19	Participated

Legend: "Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)", "Participated (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)"

The second indication revealed that "the respondents teach their child rhythm, rhyme, sounds, and syllables" with a mean score of 4.21. This focused on the learners' literacy abilities and how their parents taught them at home so they could keep up with their reading performance at school. The next logical step in closing gaps and offering focused reading instruction when success is not attained is pull-out reading intervention (Boulay et al., 2015; Denton et al., 2016). Students who felt empowered (Nelson & Manset-Williamson, 2016) had better literacy (Faggella-Luby et al., 2017). Assessment, intentional student participation, and strategies that promote in-depth comprehension of the material and a change in learning perspective are the first steps in determining need (Paterson & Elliott 2016).

The statement "the respondents teach their child to learn to syllabicate words into distinct sounds and work with them to create various

words” came in third place, with a mean of 4.19. This is dependent on how frequently the parents teach their child to read, particularly syllabating words, which are determined by the teacher's instructional program. This also demonstrated how the teacher includes experiential learning for the student and how the parent was mentored in applying it.

Furthermore, creating a strong and successful educational program is to assess and measure the skills and skill deficiencies, as well as selecting the best remediation path to content mastery (Kibler, 2019). Deciphering current information requires being exposed to literacy in a range of rich and pertinent situations.

According to Clark and Kamhi (2014), experiential learning functions best when new experiences are mixed with pre-existing knowledge in highly interested fields. The power of transnational and transactional learning is achieved when new concepts are attached to successful reading and writing activities (Akey, 2017; Kibler, 2019), when a third space was previously present (Jiménez et al., 2019)

The lowest item yielded "the respondents teach their child of from this point on, letter-sound associations that can be taught concurrently as phonemes and phonics skills" with a mean of 4.08. This is about how the teacher, and parents work together to improve the learners' schema and metacognitive skills. Learners who develop literary strategies through explicit and implicit learning experiences that occur throughout the school day and are immersed in content areas, isolation (Akey, 2017), and alternative educational and social settings (O'Brien, Langhinrichsen-Rohling, & Shelley-Tremblay, 2017) are more likely to engage in schema and metacognition (Ash, 2015). For children in basic and primary schools, mastering decoding skills is essential to reading fluently. Encouraging children in intermediate school to think independently, develop new skills, move forward, and change their perspective on responsibility is the aim.

Table 11. *Parents' Involvement in the Development of their Children's Reading Skills in terms of Phonics and Word Recognition Development*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I teach my child letter and sound recognition. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng pagkilala sa titik at tunog.)	4.35	Participated
I teach my child letters alone and frequently combined in explicit, methodical, and discrete approach. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng isang titik at karaniwang kombinasyon ng titik sa diskreto, sistematiko, at eksplisit na pamamaraan.)	4.13	Participated
I teach my child blending of simple words so that my child can basic terms so that my child can have practice development of new abilities, automaticity, and assurance. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng paglalapat ng payak na salita na maaring sanayin sa mga bagong kasanayan, automaticity, at kumpiyansa.)	4.13	Participated
I teach my child to reinforce children learn these new skills as early as possible by letting them read linked texts and listen to writings of the highest standard. (Ang aking anak ay tinuturuan ko na bigyang diin ang mga bagong kakayahan sa simula pa lamang sa pagtuturo sa mga bata na makinig sa kalidad na teksto at mga tekstong babasahin.)	4.14	Participated
I teach my child to recognize some words so that they can concentrate on the new or less familiar words and focus on making meaning, rather than just decoding. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak kumilala ng mga salita lalo na sa mga hindi masyadong pamilyar at i-pokus sa kahulugan kaysa i-decode.)	4.20	Participated
Grand Mean	4.19	Participated

Legend: "Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)", "Participated (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 11 presents the respondent's evaluation of the involvement of parents in the phonics and word recognition development of their children's reading abilities. The grand mean score was 4.19, with a verbal interpretation of "participated," implying that parents participated in the development of their children's reading skills.

The most elevated measure demonstrated that "the participants teach their child letter and sound recognition" with a mean of 4.35. This could suggest that the parents use letter and sound recognition to help their child's reading success at school. For pupils who are poor, English language learners, and many other subpopulation groups, reading performance in primary school has stopped or got worse. According to Reed, Marchand-Martella, Martella, and Kolts (2017), struggling children who get small group instruction, layered education, and accelerated reading instruction have the best chance of succeeding.

The statement ranked second with a mean of 4.20, revealing that respondents train their child to recognize specific words so that they can concentrate on unfamiliar or new phrases and create meaning rather than simply decoding. This indicates that the parents are teaching their child to read well and with comprehension. Conversely, At the intermediate school level, pupils who are Limited English Proficient (LEP), poor, or have special needs have shown a decrease in their reading skills. Students who struggle have lower quality of life and are less prepared for high school, college, and the workforce because of performance declines. Everyday activities have an impact on students, whether they are collecting and exchanging ideas with other people, writing lists of goods or letters, or sending texts to friends.

At rank three, the statement, "The respondents teach their child to reinforce these new skills as early as possible by having children

listen to high-quality texts and read connected text themselves," had a mean score of 4.14. This suggested that the parents allowed their child to learn new things, especially through reading. They gave us the reading materials, which are excellent texts. Darling-Hammond (2020) and Coutland and Leslie (2020) discovered a literacy gap in development between teachers who have received authentic professional growth based on their students' actual needs and intermediate teachers who attend national conferences focused on establishing educational systems.

The current demand for chances for meaningful and pertinent professional development gives rise to the Professional Learning Community (PLC). PLC is known as the "most efficient framework for pupil achievement and overall school success," according to Servais, Derrington, and Sanders (2019). Success is predicted by the collaboration of inexperienced and seasoned teachers using the PLC framework (Jones, 2014).

The lowest indicator, with the same means of 4.13, said that "the respondents teach their child blending of simple sentences so that their child can practice new abilities, gaining confidence," and "the respondents educate their child single letters and common combinations of letters in a separated, organized, and explicit fashion." This suggested that parents should practice new abilities and educate their children how to mix simple words and single letters.

Conversely, according to King et al. (2012), progress has not been shown in a while among pupils in intermediate school, and up to 50% of them can only read simple texts. The incapacity to conceal reading deficiencies in intermediate school learning contexts was one of the short-term consequences of reading difficulties, as it related to passing classes and peer self-esteem. Applying for jobs, getting hired, and moving up in a career were among the long-term impacts of reading difficulties, as were ongoing self-efficacy worries. As the years went by, struggling readers' avoidance behavior and compensatory skills increased, but without focused work, their actual reading improvement decreased.

Table 12. Parents' Involvement in the Development of their Children's Reading Skills in terms of Vocabulary Development

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I teach my child If they understand the meaning of a term, they are much more likely to be able to read and comprehend it inside a text. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng kahulugan ng salita, na maari nilang bigkasin at gamitin mula sa teksto.)	4.23	Participated
I teach my child constantly extending the vocabulary that they can grasp and apply in context. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng patuloy na pagpapalawak ng kaalaman sa salita na maaring gamitin sa teksto.)	4.18	Participated
I teach my child vocabulary development is both a result and a prelude to comprehension, with word meanings accounting for up to 70-90% of understanding. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak sa pagbuo ng bokabularyo na parehong komprehensiyon at kahulugan ng salita na bumubuo ng 70-90 bahagdan ng komprehensiyon.)	4.07	Participated
I teach my child vocabulary language is primarily learned by continuous exposure to new words in conversation, listening to stories, reading, and using other media. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng bokabularyo na matutunan sa paulit-ulit na pagkilala sa mga bagong salita, sa pakikinig ng mga kwento o istorya, sa pagbabasa at sa iba't ibang midya.)	4.15	Participated
I teach my child Exposure to words in relevant contexts clarifies meanings, allowing toddlers to quickly add them to their word bank. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na kilalanin ang mga salita sa makabuluhang konteksto para makabuo ng malinaw na kahulugan at maidagdag sa tipan ng mga salita.)	4.09	Participated
Grand Mean	4.15	Participated

Legend: "Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)", "Participated (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 12 demonstrates the respondent's evaluation of the parent's involvement in helping their kids grow in their vocabulary in terms of reading skills. The parents appeared to have taken part in their children's reading skill development, as shown by the grand mean of 4.15 and the verbal interpretation of "Participated."

With a mean score of 4.23, the top rater concluded that "if respondents teach their children the meaning of a word, they are far more likely to be able to read it and make sense of it throughout a text." This could imply that parents instruct their children in word meaning and textual reading comprehension. Furthermore, Maynard, Solis, Miller, and Brendel (2017) found no substantial effects on emotional issues but significant effects on children getting ongoing focused reading intervention in terms of resilience, stress measurements, and cognitive performance.

The re authorization of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act of 2004 allows students to be identified as having a specific learning disability through Response to Intervention (RTI). The IDEA Act of 2004 gave educators the authority to promote testing and intervention for pupils who have completed elementary education by using the non-progress of a student as data. According to Peregoy and Boyle (2020), recognizing commonalities between the writing systems promoted advantageous transfer in decoding, as well as "funds of knowledge as well as rich experiences with reading in primary and secondary print reading and analysis."

On the second item, the mean score of 4.18 indicated that the respondents were teaching their children to continuously extend the terminology that kids can understand and use in context. This indicated that the parents' guide their child in the vocabulary so they can

read and comprehend it. Furthermore, secondary school students across the country received less direct support for comprehension and fluency (Paterson & Elliott, 2016), and often did not receive assistance for spelling, handwriting, interpreting, or grammar (Ritchey & Goeke, 2016). The learning environment influenced the ability to identify problem readers at the intermediate school level and deliver targeted, tailored teaching. The learning environment included time spent learning skills rather than generalizing skills within curriculum areas, strategies taught and used in context, and "decreased possibilities to develop critical thinking and reading skills" (Paterson & Elliott, 2016).

The item ranked third, with a mean score of 4.15, stated that "the respondents teach their child vocabulary which is primarily learned by continuous exposure to new words in conversation, listening to stories, reading, and using other media. This demonstrated that parents should increase their child's vocabulary to ensure that they are conversant with and cognizant of the terms. This suggested that Ko and Hughes (2015) focused on a range of scenarios that showed interactive, intuitive, and practiced mastery of reading abilities across a range of constructs and situations.

The lowest rater indicated that "The respondents teach their child development of vocabulary is both an outcome of comprehension and an introduction to it, with word meanings accounting for up to 70-90% of comprehension." with a mean of 4.07. This meant that respondents would do whatever it took to improve their child's reading comprehension so that when they arrived at school, they could recite to their teachers.

Fatimayin's study (2020) revealed that parents' involvement in their children's reading development significantly impacts vocabulary growth. Through shared reading activities, parents expose children to diverse vocabulary, model proper language usage, provide context for new words, encourage interactive learning, and instill a lifelong love of reading. This active engagement enriches children's vocabulary skills, setting a strong foundation for language development and academic success (Sun & Yin, 2020).

Table 13. *Parents' Involvement in the Development of their Children's Reading Skills in terms of Fluency Development*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I teach my child to make what you're reading seem like spoken language. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na magbasa na kagaya ng ginagamit na linggwahe sa araw-araw.)	4.30	Participated
I teach my child appropriate phrasing, expression, and pace. (Tinturuan ko ang aking anak sa pagbigkas, ekspresyon, at daloy.)	4.17	Participated
I teach my child the essential components are accuracy, pace and emotion, and loudness. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak sa pangunahing bahagi kasama ng akyurasi, dalot, ekspresyon, at dami.)	4.05	Participated
I teach my child the text should be at the reader's independent reading level. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na mag-isang alamin ang teksto sa antas ng pagbasa.)	4.14	Participated
I teach my child that when children go home with books that they can 'already read,' they could develop proper expression, chunking and halting skills, and, most crucially, confidence. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na kapag pinadalhan ng libro ay kaya nila itong basahin, may kakayahang magbuo ng tamang ekspresyon, magsanay ng pagputol at paghinto, at sa pagbuo ng kumpiyansa.)	4.12	Participated
Grand Mean	4.16	Participated

Legend: "Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)", "Participated (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 13 shows the respondent's assessment on the parent's involvement of their children's reading skills development in terms of Fluency Development. The grand mean was 4.16, with a verbal description of "participated," implying that parents participated in the development of their children's reading skills.

The top statement was "the respondents teach their child to simulate reading sound like spoken language with a mean of 4.30. This indicated that the parents would integrate the language used so that they could readily grasp it. Furthermore, it was suggested that strengthening reading begin in the classroom. Transactional Learning Theories imply that students learn in a natural setting and adapt their reading behavior to classroom models in programs that integrate strategies and generalized abilities via relevant content. Embedded literacy practice is a Tier I effective reading intervention (Ash, 2014). The least restrictive environment, in which students' study in clustered groups of ability learners and apply skills inside material, is one of the classroom teacher's powerful instructional approaches, which are available to all students.

This is followed by the indicator suggesting that "the respondents teach their child using suitable phrasing, expression, and pace" (mean of 4.17). This meant that the parents taught their child the correct phrasing, expression, tempo, meaning, syllabication, and pronunciation of the word. This revealed that the effectiveness of increasing classroom literacy through embedded training warrants further examination. Joshi et al. (2012) proposed that a multi-modal learning strategy improves the achievement of struggling readers. Parker (2012) promoted transactional learning in the classroom, whereas Macy and Bricker (2016) stressed need-based intervention in a naturalistic context.

The third ranking revealed that "the respondents teach their child the text be at the readers' independent reading level," with a mean of 4.14. This indicates that the parents teach their child readers at the independent reading level in which the parents encourage their child

to become self-sufficient in learning. This includes the instructor in the interventions, as well as their parents. Furthermore, Parker (2012) discovered that targeted intervention in isolation was ineffective in children with low starting reading skills, whereas embedded instruction within the context of subject texts was more effective. It was claimed that the various growth patterns corresponded to the students' initial skills and demands. It was determined that student needs must be identified prior to intervention programs to appropriately match intervention to need. The success of the reading intervention program may be determined by its individualization and customization.

The lowest statement was that "the respondents teach their child the essential components, which include accuracy, pace, expressiveness, and loudness with a mean of 4.05. This teaches the parents about reading accuracy, pace, and expression, which includes student interaction and classroom activities. Furthermore, student engagement is an important aspect in determining student reading performance. When readers struggle, their involvement in classroom activities is typically diminished. Students soon notice and contrast their own abilities (both academic and non-academic) with those of their siblings and classmates. Students observe reading skills; as a result, without ever identifying specific reading levels, children quickly determine who is a "better reader."

Wiseman's (2012) examination of the impact of falling behind classmates on a kindergarten student named Kevin, who had disengaged from literacy instruction due to his poor reading skills at the age of five highlighted the importance for teachers to recognize that students learn at different rates and to support them in developing readiness to learn at their own pace and in ways that enable individual achievement.

Table 14 represents the respondent's perspective on the parent's participation in their children's reading comprehension skills are improving. The grand mean was 4.17, with the verbal meaning of "participated." This indicated that the parents took an active role in their children's reading development. The highest response, with a mean of 4.23, suggested that "the respondents teach their child to be effective listeners who understand the objective of their reading and tailor their reading behaviors (skimming, scanning, or reading intently for detail) to that purpose."

Table 14. *Parents' Involvement in the Development of their Children's Reading Skills in terms of Comprehension Development*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I teach my child to be effective listeners who Understand the objective of their reading and tailor their reading habits (skimming, scanning, or reading intently for detail) to that purpose. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na maging epektibong mambabasa na nauunawaan ang gamit ng binabasa at paggamit ng gawi ng pagbasa.)	4.23	Participated
I teach my child to Learn the texts that appear different depending on their defined purpose, context, and audience. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na matutuhan ang teksto na mukhang kakaiba sa gamit, konteksto, at audience.)	4.09	Participated
I teach my child to be proficient listeners who they read, keep track of their comprehension, and integrate new material with previous knowledge and experience. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na maging mahusay na mambabasa na nag-momonitor ng pag-unawa sa kanilang binabasa, pagsasama ng mga impormasyon sa kaalaman at karanasan.)	4.22	Participated
I teach my child that they focus on relevant elements of the text to discern between important content and trivial detail. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak ng nag mag-pokus sa mga mahahalagang teksto para malaman ang mga importanteng nilalaman sa mga hindi mahalaga.)	4.19	Participated
I teach my child that they make and monitor predictions, as well as analyze content, while listening. (Tinuturuan ko ang aking anak na gawin at i-monitor ang mga prediksiyon at tayain ang nilalaman ng kanilang binasa.)	4.10	Participated
Grand Mean	4.17	Participated

Legend: "Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)", "Participated (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)"

This meant that the parents taught their children to be good listeners for the sake of reading. This addressed performance inequalities in the classroom through educational opportunities. According to Wiseman (2012), research by Good and Nicols (2021) discovered that performance differences among "at-risk" students are related to instructional opportunities in class. I agree with Wiseman that a deficit-based method of teaching is more frequent in schools than one that focuses on strengths. In my efforts to enhance reading skills, I regularly become upset and overwhelmed by what students are unable to achieve, overlooking what they can do and how far they have progressed as readers. Wiseman also cited Allington and Cunningham's (2022) study as an example of a poor teaching style that decreases engagement: "When students spend more time on individual skills instruction and extensive repetition, the end result is disengagement and frustration."

Second in the ranking was "the respondents teach their child to be proficient listeners who assess their understanding as they read, integrating new material with current knowledge and experience" (mean = 4.22). This revealed that parents teach their children the value of being good listeners to develop their knowledge, particularly through reading. This suggested that the learners' reading performance included interactive read-aloud. Furthermore, Interactive read-aloud, which uses teacher-directed modeling and higher-level inquiry, challenges and stretches all students' reading thinking and understanding. Wiseman's (2012) nine-month qualitative study includes four weekly observations of the kindergarten classroom between October and May. Data was gathered throughout the morning

meeting, read-aloud, and writing sessions. Kevin, a student participant, recorded field notes on teacher instruction, student involvement, and read-aloud responses.

The statement "the respondents teach their child that They concentrate on relevant sections of the text to identify important content from trivial stuff." ranked third, with a mean of 4.19. This allowed the parents to teach their child how to distinguish important content for them to comprehend what they read.

Wiseman (2019) study proved that despite a child's difficulties with inadequate reading skills, which led to disengagement and frustration during teaching, the study discovered that read-aloud "provided the child with chances to contribute to class in ways that extended his thoughts about reading". The child's comments grew more sophisticated over the course of the year, demonstrating greater comprehension, personal connections, and increased participation.

The student's "responses paralleled the teacher's emphasis on complex thinking and open-ended responses" (Wiseman 2019). Wiseman concluded from the case study that read-aloud is a great teaching strategy for improving student literacy comprehension and engagement.

The lowest response stated that "the respondents teach their child to learn the writings that look different depending on their defined purpose, context, and audience" with a mean of 4.09. This revealed that the parents let their child discover the identified purpose, context, and audience.

This is corroborating with the idea that engaging books should be selected. Teachers purposefully choose read-aloud novels to increase students' interest and involvement in both guided and independent reading activities. To allow students to choose what they want to read, teachers should have a wide variety of books available at all reading levels. Relatable characters and an interest in the book's subject matter are key components that promote reading engagement. Readers of all ability levels may now easily access e-books, and numerous websites and publishing businesses see them as a useful tool for raising student engagement.

3. Parent's Involvement During the Implementation and Post-Implementation Stages of the Intervention Program

Table 15 presents data on parental engagement during the implementation phase of the intervention program. The overall average score, indicated by the grand mean of 4.17, indicates active parental participation throughout the program's implementation stage.

Table 15. *Parent's Involvement During the Program's Implementation Stage*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I teach my child how to participate and cooperate in activities inside the classroom. (Tinuturuan kong makilahok ang aking anak sa mga diskusyon sa silid aralan.)	4.36	Participated
I teach my child how to study and learn on their own. (Tinuturuan ko na maging independiyente sa kanyang pag-aaral ang aking anak.)	4.30	Participated
I teach my child phonemes, sounds, and pronunciation in the lessons to master the topic. (Tinuturuan ko na mag pokus sa leksiyon sa pagbabasa para mahasa sa mga paksa ang aking anak.)	4.29	Participated
I teach my child to exchange ideas with their classmates. (Tinuturuan ko na makipagpalitan ng ideya sa kanyang mga kamag-aral ang aking anak.)	4.20	Participated
I teach my child the right way to ask questions to their teacher particularly to difficult reading topics. (Tinuturuan ko na magtanong sa kanilang guro lalo na sa mga mahihirap na paksa sa pagbasa ang aking anak.)	4.34	Participated
Grand Mean	4.17	Participated

Legend: "Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)", "Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)", "Participated (3.51 – 4.50)", "Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)"

The highest item indicated that "the respondents teach their child how to participate and cooperate in activities inside the classroom" with a mean of 4.36. This suggested that parents instruct their children on reading comprehension and engagement outside of the classroom

Jones and Brown (2021) revealed that having a diverse selection of books to choose from was crucial for reading satisfaction, rather than a preference between e-books and traditional print books. While e-books can complement print books to expand reading options and enhance student engagement, teachers should still utilize them, as student choice in reading material boosts motivation and engagement (Jones & Brown, 2020).

Additionally, the study found that parents play a role in teaching children how to effectively ask questions, particularly about challenging reading topics, suggesting the importance of parental involvement in supporting children's reading development. Teachers should design reading activities to ensure all students, especially struggling readers, feel motivated and successful. This may involve modeling proficient reading, facilitating literature-based discussions, and carefully selecting appropriate books to encourage reading engagement.

The third rank stated that "the respondents teach their child how to study and learn on their own" with a mean score of 4.30. This demonstrated that parents allow their children to study on their own. This needs to develop the child the love for reading books be in printed or electronic material. Children will not readily read novels that they find too challenging or that they are not interested in

reading, just as adults would not. To have fully engaged readers, teachers must maintain a vast library and allow students to choose what they want to read, whether it is e-books or traditional print materials. When students are allowed to select a book based on their reading ability and area of interest, it is crucial to provide specific instruction so that they can learn the skills and techniques needed to improve as readers and read with complete engagement.

The lowest item showed that “the respondents teach their child to exchange ideas with their classmates” with a mean score of 4.20. This implied that the parents allowed their child to engage with their classmates to exchange information so that they learn more. This pertains to the development of phonological awareness among learners so that learners can exchange ideas about the matter. The significance of Phonological awareness and phonics skills for first-time readers has been extensively studied. According to Park and Lombardino (2015), The understanding of phonology is a “strong and significant predictor of word reading skills in elementary children.” When students first begin to read, these decoding skills are critical, and teachers must explicitly teach them to them. Reading comprehension is dependent on word recognition, which requires phonological awareness.

The results above indicate several key findings regarding parental involvement in supporting children's reading development. Firstly, parents play a crucial role in teaching children's skills such as participation, cooperation, and independent learning, as evidenced by high mean scores for these items. Additionally, the study underscores the importance of providing children with a diverse selection of books to choose from, whether in print or electronic format, to enhance reading satisfaction and engagement (Garces-Bacsal, (2020).. Moreover, parents contribute significantly to children's reading development by teaching them effective questioning strategies and fostering opportunities for peer interaction to facilitate knowledge exchange (Geske and Ozola, 2020).

Lastly, the findings highlight the critical role of phonological awareness and phonics skills in early reading development, emphasizing the need for explicit instruction in these areas to support reading comprehension and word recognition. This was supported by the study of Melby-Lervåg, Lyster, & Hulme, 2012). Parental involvement, teacher guidance, and a rich literary environment are essential components for cultivating engaged and proficient readers.

Table 16. Parent's Involvement in the Program's Stages of Implementation During Post-implementation

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I teach my child how to participate and cooperate in activities inside the classroom. (Tinuturuan kong makilahok ang aking anak sa mga diskusyon sa silid aralan.)	4.36	Participated
I teach my child how to study and learn on their own. (Tinuturuan ko na maging independiyente sa kanyang pag-aaral ang aking anak.)	4.30	Participated
I teach my child phonemes, sounds, and pronunciation in the lessons to master the topic. (Tinuturuan ko na mag pokus sa leksiyon sa pagbabasa para mahasa sa mga paksa ang aking anak.)	4.29	Participated
I teach my child to exchange ideas with their classmates. (Tinuturuan ko na makipagpalitan ng ideya sa kanyang mga kamag-aral ang aking anak.)	4.20	Participated
I teach my child the right way to ask questions to their teacher particularly to difficult reading topics. (Tinuturuan ko na magtanong sa kanilang guro lalo na sa mga mahihirap na paksa sa pagbasa ang aking anak.)	4.34	Participated
Grand Mean	4.12	Participated

Legend: “Not Participated (1.00 – 1.50)”, “Barely Participated (1.51 – 2.50)”, “Moderately Participated (2.51 – 3.50)”, “Participated (3.51 – 4.50)”, “Highly Participated (4.51 – 5.00)”

Table 16 displays the respondent's assessment on the parent's participation during the program's stage of Post Implementation. The grand mean score was 4.12, with a verbal interpretation of “participated,” implying that parents took part in the program's implementation stages.

Highest indicator showed that “the respondents teach their child should study and read at home before playing.” with a mean of 4.26. This makes the parents develop their child self-discipline and time management. This is to make their child learn more about phonic skills so that they will not be left behind. Park and Lombardino (2013) proposed that teachers employ the following phonics skills-improving strategies during instruction time to help struggling readers: phonological awareness, phonics/decoding instruction, spelling instruction, instruction in vocabulary, and morphological education.

The next indicator elicited that “the respondents teach their child discipline particularly in reading and studying” and “the respondents teach their child to become patient in reading and studying” with the same means of 4.23. This showed that the parents impose discipline on their child and that they instill patience in them in studying the lessons or when it comes to reading. This is to develop more their phonic skills. Together, these elements improve pupils' phonological abilities while teaching word studies. During reading instruction time, good teachers use all of these to engage, model, coach, and provide direct instruction that enhances students' growth of reading ability.

The lowest indicator stated that “the respondents teach their child to read in advance so that he is ahead of his classmates” with a mean of 3.86. This lets the parents their child to make advance studies. This denoted that this is the purpose of the Parents-Teachers Conference in school to instill in learners the value of studying and learning. Numerous school constructs, including engagement, are correlated with parental involvement. These constructs include assisting with schoolwork, attending parent-teacher conferences, participating in extracurricular activities, monitoring students' grades, establishing parental values, and giving internal and external

incentive. However, Lai and Vadeboncoeur (2012) noted that schools have not appropriately involved parents.

Villiger (2020) found that parent involvement during the post-implementation stage of a reading program holds significant importance for various reasons. Firstly, it enables parents to monitor their child's progress and growth in reading skills, identifying areas of difficulty and providing necessary support. Additionally, parental involvement reinforces the lessons learned during the program by engaging in reading activities and offering additional practice at home.

Moreover, McGeown and Smith (2023) study revealed that sustaining children's motivation and enthusiasm for reading is facilitated through parental support and encouragement. Addressing any challenges promptly and effectively is another benefit, as parents can collaborate with educators to find solutions and advocate for their child's needs. Furthermore, research consistently highlights the correlation between sustained parental involvement and improved academic outcomes, emphasizing the crucial role parents play in their child's ongoing development and long-term success as a reader.

4. Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Parents' Participation in the Development of Their Children's Reading Skills

Table 17. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent's Assessment When Grouped According to Age*

Indicators	Age	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Oral Language Development	20 and below	187.63	1.601	0.206	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	21-30	187.72				
	31-40	184.92				
	41-50	185.01				
	51-60	197.82				
	61 and above	112.33				
Phonological Awareness Development	20 and below	173.94	2.785	0.095	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	21-30	190.54				
	31-40	186.97				
	41-50	177.56				
	51-60	195.45				
	61 and above	98.17				
Phonics and Word Recognition Development	20 and below	177.06	2.286	0.131	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	21-30	193.07				
	31-40	184.09				
	41-50	178.27				
	51-60	209.23				
	61 and above	127.00				
Vocabulary Development	20 and below	180.81	2.553	0.110	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	21-30	188.41				
	31-40	183.49				
	41-50	188.25				
	51-60	206.18				
	61 and above	99.33				
Fluency Development	20 and below	178.44	2.259	0.133	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	21-30	192.58				
	31-40	188.31				
	41-50	170.86				
	51-60	177.68				
	61 and above	145.33				
Comprehension Development	20 and below	170.00	1.342	0.247	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	21-30	187.38				
	31-40	187.34				
	41-50	175.25				
	51-60	208.32				
	61 and above	186.50				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 17 compares respondent assessments of parent involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One pupils by age using the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test. Calculated p-value for oral language development was 0.206, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by age, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the students in Grade One. The calculated p-value for Phonological Awareness Development was 0.095, exceeding the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject

the null hypothesis. When grouped by age, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the students in Grade One.

The p-value for Phonics and Word Recognition Development was 0.131, over the significance level of 0.05 once more. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by age, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the students in Grade One. The estimated p-value for Vocabulary Development was 0.110, surpassing the significant level of 0.05 once more. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by age, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the students in Grade One.

The p-value was 0.133, which exceeded the 0.05 standard of significance according to Fluency Development. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by age, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the students in Grade One. With respect to Comprehension Development, the p-value was 0.247, surpassing the significant threshold of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis.

In the literature, there is evidence of a positive correlation between the level of parental involvement and reading comprehension. For example, Bond (2021) examined the relationship between family involvement and reading comprehension achievement, motivation and attitudes on primary school second and third graders, reporting a positive effect of parental involvement on reading achievement, attitudes and motivation. York (2016), in his study investigating the effect of parental involvement on reading achievement, concluded that as the level of parental involvement increased, the level of reading achievement also increased.

Table 18. *Mann Whitney U – Test: Comparison on the Respondent's Assessment on the Parent's Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Sex*

Indicators	Sex	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Oral Language Development	Female	189.31	8953.5	0.076	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	159.97				
Phonological Awareness Development	Female	189.53	9026.5	0.060	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	158.45				
Phonics and Word Recognition Development	Female	188.42	8667.5	0.174	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	165.93				
Vocabulary Development	Female	188.65	8742.5	0.142	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	164.36				
Fluency Development	Female	188.23	8605.5	0.204	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	167.22				
Comprehension Development	Female	187.29	8305.5	0.403	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	173.47				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 18 demonstrates the Mann Whitney U-Test comparison of the respondent's estimate of the level of parental involvement in the Grade One learners' reading intervention program when sorted by gender. The p-value for oral language development was 0.076, which is significantly above the 0.05 level. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One learners. The p-value for Phonological Awareness Development was 0.060, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One learners.

Phonics and Word Recognition Development states that at the 0.05 level, the p-value of 0.174 indicates significance. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One learners. The p-value for Vocabulary Development was 0.142, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One learners.

In reference to Fluency Development, the p-value was 0.204, surpassing the significance threshold of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One learners. The p-value, as reported by Comprehension Development, was 0.403, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, there is no noticeable variation in the respondent's perception of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One learners.

Likewise, it is stated that parental participation contributes to the academic achievement and course performance of students in general (Bailey, 2017; Topor et al., 2020). In this context, positive results have been obtained in studies on parental involvement conducted at home and at school to improve reading and reading comprehension as an academic skill (Epstein, 2021; Baker, 2023; Mraz and

Rasinski, 2017; Tonn and Wailheiser, 2017).

Table 19. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent's Assessment when Grouped According to Occupation*

Indicators	Occupation	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Oral Language Development	Regular	187.07	14.546	0.006	Reject Ho	Significant
	Probationary	164.41				
	Housewife	185.94				
	None	190.83				
	Others	242.99				
Phonological Awareness Development	Regular	195.51	13.082	0.011	Reject Ho	Significant
	Probationary	161.31				
	Housewife	178.58				
	None	194.23				
	Others	227.86				
Phonics and Word Recognition Development	Regular	196.18	14.255	0.007	Reject Ho	Significant
	Probationary	167.48				
	Housewife	165.52				
	None	193.83				
	Others	234.30				
Vocabulary Development	Regular	199.23	19.373	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	Probationary	157.02				
	Housewife	173.64				
	None	200.95				
	Others	236.46				
Fluency Development	Regular	192.51	12.278	0.015	Reject Ho	Significant
	Probationary	163.72				
	Housewife	179.60				
	None	197.80				
	Others	231.87				
Comprehension Development	Regular	195.05	15.903	0.003	Reject Ho	Significant
	Probationary	164.43				
	Housewife	170.79				
	None	190.85				
	Others	240.23				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 19 shows the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test comparison on the respondent's estimate of the parent's level of participation in the Grade One learners' reading intervention program, broken down by profession. The p-value for oral language development was 0.006, which is statistically insignificant at the 0.05 level. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. When categorized by occupation, there is a notable discrepancy in the respondents' evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading program intervention for first graders. Phonological Awareness Development has a p-value of 0.011, which is less significant than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by occupation, there is a notable discrepancy in the respondents' evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners.

According to Phonics and Word Recognition Development, the p-value was 0.007, meaning that the significance threshold was less than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by occupation, there is a notable discrepancy in the respondents' evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners. Compared to the 0.05 level, the p-value for Vocabulary Development was 0.001, which is less significant. The null hypothesis was thus disproved. When categorized by occupation, there is a notable discrepancy in the respondents' evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading program intervention for Grade One learners.

Fluency Development's p-value was 0.015, which is less significant than the 0.05 cutoff. Thus, the null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by occupation, there is a notable discrepancy in the respondents' evaluations of the parents' involvement in the first-grade reading intervention program. For understanding improvement, the p-value was 0.003, which is below the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by occupation, there is a notable discrepancy in the respondents' evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for first graders.

However, in several studies, a positive relationship was not found between parental involvement and academic achievement (Okpala et al., 2021), whereas few studies reported a negative relationship (Hill and Tyson, 2019; Jeynes, 2015). The discrepancies in research findings may be because parents are not adequately trained to teach certain concepts, or they are not familiar with the teaching methods in the studies concerned.

Table 20. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent’s Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Occupation*

Occupation	Oral Language Development		Phonological Awareness Development	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Regular vs. Probationary	0.0884	Not Significant	0.0084	Not Significant
Regular vs. Housewife	0.9426	Not Significant	0.2539	Not Significant
Regular vs. None	0.8804	Not Significant	0.9273	Not Significant
Regular vs. Others	0.0047	Significant	0.1146	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Housewife	0.1847	Not Significant	0.2885	Not Significant
Probationary vs. None	0.2971	Not Significant	0.1961	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Others	0.0001	Significant	0.0011	Significant
Housewife vs. None	0.8545	Not Significant	0.5590	Not Significant
Housewife vs. Others	0.0089	Not Significant	0.0247	Not Significant
None vs. Others	0.0746	Not Significant	0.2526	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/10 =0.005) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 20 shows the findings of the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine the significant difference in parent participation in Grade One learners reading intervention program when the parents are grouped based on their occupation. Using Bonferroni Correction in Dunn's Test post ad hoc test on oral language development revealed significant differences between probationary and others as well as regular and others (p-value = 0.0047) (p-value = 0.0001). However, the post ad hoc test utilizing Bonferroni Correction in Dunn's test revealed significant differences between Probationary and Others in addition to Phonological Awareness Development, with a p-value of 0.0011.

However, instead of focusing on the relationship between the level of parental involvement and any academic skill without an intervention, the effects of practices in which parents constantly worked with their children through parent-involved reading activities were investigated in the present study.

Table 21. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent’s Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Occupation*

Occupation	Phonics and Word Recognition Development		Vocabulary Development	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Regular vs. Probationary	0.0323	Not Significant	0.0016	Significant
Regular vs. Housewife	0.0517	Not Significant	0.1043	Not Significant
Regular vs. None	0.9256	Not Significant	0.9454	Not Significant
Regular vs. Others	0.0557	Not Significant	0.0616	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Housewife	0.9041	Not Significant	0.3085	Not Significant
Probationary vs. None	0.3022	Not Significant	0.0852	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Others	0.0010	Significant	0.0000	Significant
Housewife vs. None	0.2917	Not Significant	0.3088	Not Significant
Housewife vs. Others	0.0018	Significant	0.0043	Significant
None vs. Others	0.1698	Not Significant	0.2283	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/10 =0.005) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 21 shows the findings of the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine the significant difference in parent participation in Grade One learner’s reading intervention program when the parents are grouped based on their occupation. The post ad hoc test utilizing Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction revealed significant differences in Phonics and Word Recognition Development between Housewife and Others (p-value=0.0018) and Probationary and Others (p-value=0.0010). Additionally, there were significant differences in Vocabulary Development between Probationary and Others (p-value = 0.0000) and Housewife and Others (p-value = 0.0043) according to the post ad hoc test using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction.

In addition to the potentially positive relationship between parental involvement and reading comprehension, intervention programs aiming to enhance the level of participation can yield fruitful results. In this regard, communication channels between parents and school need to be further strengthened to enable the participation of parents.

Table 22 presents the outcomes of the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to ascertain the significant difference in parent participation in Grade One learner’s reading intervention program when the parents are grouped based on their occupation. With relation to Fluency Development, a p-value of 0.0009 indicated significant differences between Probationary and Others in the post ad hoc test utilizing Bonferroni Correction in Dunn's test. The post ad hoc test employing with Bonferroni Correction in Dunn's test revealed significant differences in comprehension development between Housewife and Others (p-value = 0.0016) and Probationary and Others (0.0002).

Parental involvement in a child’s early education is consistently found to be positively associated with a child’s academic performance (Hill& Craft, 2003). Children whose parents are involved in their education and by extension reading, have higher levels of academic performance than those whose parents are involved to a lesser degree. Again, Olsen and Fuller (citing Henderson & Berla, 2008) submit that the most accurate prediction of a students’ achievement in school is not income or social status but the extent to which the students’ family is able to create a home environment that encourages learning, express high and realistic expectations for their children’s

achievement and future careers and become involved in their education at school and in the society

Table 22. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent’s Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Occupation*

Occupation	Fluency Development		Comprehension Development	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Regular vs. Probationary	0.0323	Not Significant	0.0220	Not Significant
Regular vs. Housewife	0.4145	Not Significant	0.1230	Not Significant
Regular vs. None	0.8341	Not Significant	0.8672	Not Significant
Regular vs. Others	0.0490	Not Significant	0.0231	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Housewife	0.3324	Not Significant	0.6963	Not Significant
Probationary vs. None	0.1836	Not Significant	0.2999	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Others	0.0009	Significant	0.0002	Significant
Housewife vs. None	0.4494	Not Significant	0.4541	Not Significant
Housewife vs. Others	0.0179	Not Significant	0.0016	Significant
None vs. Others	0.2496	Not Significant	0.0934	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/10 =0.005) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 23. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent’s Assessment on the when Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

Indicators	Educational Attainment	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Oral Language Development	Elementary	150.00	22.023	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	164.82				
	College	205.45				
	Post-Graduate	211.59				
	Vocational	129.47				
Phonological Awareness Development	Elementary	162.29	22.124	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	163.28				
	College	204.10				
	Post-Graduate	227.65				
	Vocational	132.09				
Phonics and Word Recognition Development	Elementary	175.43	23.224	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	167.19				
	College	202.57				
	Post-Graduate	232.76				
	Vocational	122.53				
Vocabulary Development	Elementary	170.79	20.856	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	159.49				
	College	204.58				
	Post-Graduate	224.32				
	Vocational	142.08				
Fluency Development	Elementary	166.79	27.077	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	164.19				
	College	205.24				
	Post-Graduate	230.62				
	Vocational	111.58				
Comprehension Development	Elementary	165.29	22.813	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	164.53				
	College	204.59				
	Post-Graduate	222.12				
	Vocational	127.05				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 23 presents the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison on the respondent's view of the parent's level of participation in the Grade One learners' reading intervention program, organized by educational attainment. The p-value was 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance for Oral Language Development. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. When respondents are classified by educational achievement, there is a significant variation in their perceptions of their parents' level of participation in the reading intervention program for first graders. Phonological Awareness Development had a p-value of 0.000, which is less significant than the 0.05 level. The null hypothesis was thus disproved. When grouped by educational attainment, there is a significant difference in the respondent's assessment of the parent's level of participation in the reading intervention program for Grade One students.

For the development of word recognition and phonics, the p-value was 0.000, which is less significant than the 0.05 level. Thus, the

null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by educational achievement the respondent's assessment of the parent's degree of involvement in the first grader reading intervention program differs significantly. The p-value was 0.000, according to Vocabulary Development, which is less significant than the 0.05 cutoff. Thus, the null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by educational achievement, Regarding the parent's involvement in the first grader reading intervention program, the respondent's assessment differs significantly.

Fluency Development's p-value was 0.000, which is lower than the 0.05 standard. Thus, the null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by educational achievement, regarding the parent's involvement in the first grader reading intervention program, the respondent's assessment varied significantly. P-value, as per Comprehension Development, was 0.000, suggesting a significant threshold of less than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was refuted. When categorized by educational achievement, the respondent's assessment of the level of parent's involvement in the reading intervention program differs significantly for the Grade One pupils.

Parental role and involvement are defined as facilitating learning at home, providing needed reading materials and a conducive learning environment. Home-based parental involvement includes helping children with homework, talking with them about school, expressing elevated expectations, encouraging school success, and providing structures conducive to learning (Altschul, 2012). Parents without formal education are those who either did not go to school or attended and stopped at the primary school level.

Table 24. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent's Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Oral Language Development		Phonological Awareness Development	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Elementary vs. High School	0.7154	Not Significant	0.9806	Not Significant
Elementary vs. College	0.1670	Not Significant	0.2999	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Post-Graduate	0.1888	Not Significant	0.1652	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Vocational	0.6364	Not Significant	0.4890	Not Significant
High School vs. College	0.0009	Significant	0.0009	Significant
High School vs. Post-Graduate	0.0850	Not Significant	0.0183	Not Significant
High School vs. Vocational	0.0869	Not Significant	0.1329	Not Significant
College vs. Post-Graduate	0.8160	Not Significant	0.3741	Not Significant
College vs. Vocational	0.0001	Significant	0.0030	Significant
Post-Graduate vs. Vocational	0.0084	Not Significant	0.0023	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/10 = 0.005) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 24 presents the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test for assessing the significant difference in Grade One learner's parents' engagement in reading intervention program when the learners are classified based on educational attainment. The post ad hoc analysis on spoken language development using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction revealed significant differences between college and vocational as well as college and high school (p-value = 0.0009). The post ad hoc test using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction revealed significant differences in Phonological Awareness Development between Vocational and College (p-value = 0.0030), High school and college (p-value = 0.0009), as well as post-graduate and vocational (p-value = 0.0023).

Parents are the child's first teacher. In the same vein, primary school is an important level of a child's education. Children therefore need to be put on the right on the right path to success by giving them attention, time and support for their home/schoolwork as well as helping them learn to read. Parents do not have to be the best to help. What matters most is their time, interest, and the pleasure they share with the child as part of reading together. Children learn to read bit by bit. They talk and listen to stories read aloud, pretend to read, learn how to handle books, learn about print and how it works, identify letters by name and shape, identify separate sounds in spoken language, write with scribbles and drawing, connect single letters with the sound they make and many more (Vasylenko,2017).

Table 25. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent's Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Phonics and Word Recognition Development		Vocabulary Development	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Elementary vs. High School	0.9874	Not Significant	0.7827	Not Significant
Elementary vs. College	0.4954	Not Significant	0.4033	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Post-Graduate	0.2198	Not Significant	0.2569	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Vocational	0.2310	Not Significant	0.5117	Not Significant
High School vs. College	0.0325	Not Significant	0.0003	Significant
High School vs. Post-Graduate	0.0346	Not Significant	0.0178	Not Significant
High School vs. Vocational	0.0151	Not Significant	0.4026	Not Significant
College vs. Post-Graduate	0.2527	Not Significant	0.4572	Not Significant
College vs. Vocational	0.0000	Significant	0.0016	Significant
Post-Graduate vs. Vocational	0.0004	Significant	0.0088	Not Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/10 = 0.005) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 25 presents the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine the significant difference in parent engagement with Grade One learners' reading intervention program when the learners are classified based on educational attainment. The post ad hoc test using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction revealed significant differences between p-values for post-graduate and vocational (0.0004) and college and vocational (0.0000) on phonics and word recognition development. Vocabulary Development reports that there were significant differences between high school and college (p-value = 0.0003) and between college and vocational (p-value = 0.0016) in the post ad hoc test utilizing Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction.

Reading is a complex act that must be learned. Unlike speaking, which comes naturally in normal children, reading must be taught and taught well. Learning to read according to Fatimayin (2015) depends upon motivation, practice, correct teaching methods and reinforcement. Potter (2021) opines that reading fires children's imagination and encourages quick learning as well as widens views, expands horizons, and helps readers learn about other climes. It is a tool for learning other subjects and a yardstick for measuring academic progress.

Table 26. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent's Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Fluency Development		Comprehension Development	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Elementary vs. High School	0.9496	Not Significant	0.9853	Not Significant
Elementary vs. College	0.3396	Not Significant	0.3303	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Post-Graduate	0.1781	Not Significant	0.2281	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Vocational	0.2831	Not Significant	0.3814	Not Significant
High School vs. College	0.0009	Significant	0.0012	Significant
High School vs. Post-Graduate	0.0156	Not Significant	0.0350	Not Significant
High School vs. Vocational	0.0329	Not Significant	0.0712	Not Significant
College vs. Post-Graduate	0.3473	Not Significant	0.5087	Not Significant
College vs. Vocational	0.0000	Significant	0.0000	Significant
Post-Graduate vs. Vocational	0.0004	Significant	0.0024	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/10 = 0.005) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 26 displays the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test used to determine the notable variation in parental involvement among Grade One learners' reading intervention program when the learners are classified based on educational attainment. The post ad hoc test employing Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction, in line with Fluency Development, revealed significant differences between Vocational and College (p-value = 0.0000), Post-Graduate and Vocational (p-value = 0.0004), as well as High School and College (p-value = 0.0009), showed significant differences. The post ad hoc test employing Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction highlighted notable distinctions in comprehension development between post-graduate and vocational (p-value = 0.0024), college and vocational (p-value = 0.0000), and high school and college (p-value = 0.0012).

Parents are the primary educators of their children and are in partnership with the school. A child, Mudzielwana (2014) asserts, does not become literate on his/her own. S/he must receive help from parents and teachers. That is the reason a child's first teacher is his/her parent and his/her first school, the home. Vasylenko (2017) opines that since reading is so important for success at school and in future life, parents can and should play a significant role in helping their children develop reading skills and in encouraging their reading growth. Vasylenko went further to state that if children receive the right kind of parental help, reading difficulties that may arise later can be prevented. Many researchers (Senec hal & LeFevre, 2002; Mudzielwana, 2014; Vasylenko, 2017) have shown that when parents and families are involved, children are more successful in developing reading skills.

Table 27 illustrates the analysis of respondents' evaluations of parental involvement in the first-grade reading intervention program, categorized by family income, employing the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test. The resulting p-value of 0.261 exceeds the 0.05 significance level, along with spoken language development.

Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading assistance program for Grade One students. P-value for Phonological Awareness Development was 0.263, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners.

Regarding the advancement of phonics and word recognition, the p-value was 0.137, exceeding the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading assistance program for Grade One learners. P-value for Vocabulary Development was 0.070, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the program of reading intervention for Grade One learners.

P-value for Fluency Development was 0.082, over the significance threshold of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents'

involvement in the program of reading intervention for first graders. P-value, as reported by Comprehension Development, was 0.064, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners.

Table 27. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent's Assessment when Grouped According to Family Income*

Indicators	Family Income	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Oral Language Development	15,000 and below	176.20	5.269	0.261	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	191.16				
	30,001 to 45,000	200.59				
	45,001 to 60,000	167.07				
	60,001 and above	221.30				
Phonological Awareness Development	15,000 and below	174.99	5.249	0.263	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	189.61				
	30,001 to 45,000	210.36				
	45,001 to 60,000	183.50				
	60,001 and above	213.77				
Phonics and Word Recognition Development	15,000 and below	172.85	6.975	0.137	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	196.29				
	30,001 to 45,000	205.06				
	45,001 to 60,000	166.53				
	60,001 and above	214.82				
Vocabulary Development	15,000 and below	172.87	8.657	0.070	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	190.97				
	30,001 to 45,000	214.05				
	45,001 to 60,000	171.70				
	60,001 and above	226.43				
Fluency Development	15,000 and below	172.21	8.287	0.082	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	197.40				
	30,001 to 45,000	210.83				
	45,001 to 60,000	158.70				
	60,001 and above	210.75				
Comprehension Development	15,000 and below	170.16	8.882	0.064	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	195.37				
	30,001 to 45,000	216.61				
	45,001 to 60,000	184.90				
	60,001 and above	212.05				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Pinantoan (2023) opines that students with the two parents operating in supportive roles are 52% more likely to enjoy school and get straight 'As' than students without supportive parents. Therefore, parental involvement entails regular supervision of the child's homework and motivating children to learn. (Fan & Chen, 2021; Jeynes (2023, 2017) opine that parental involvement plays an important role in a child's education and many of positive effect on the child's academic success. On the contrary, Bobbett, French, Achilles & Bobbett (2015): Copper, Lindsay & Nye, (2020) found that the effect parental involvement has on students' academic achievement is not significant.

Table 28 presents the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test results for the comparison of respondents' perceptions of parental involvement in the Grade One reading intervention program, categorized by family size. P-value for oral language development was 0.064, which is significant over the 0.05 threshold. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When categorized by family size, The analysis suggests that there is no noticeable distinction in the respondents' views regarding the level of parental involvement in the Grade One reading intervention program. The p-value for Phonological Awareness Development was 0.079, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When categorized by family size, the analysis suggests that there is no noticeable distinction in the respondents' views regarding the level of parental involvement in the Grade One reading intervention program.

The p-value, as reported by Phonics and Word Recognition Development, was 0.086, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When categorized by family size, The analysis suggests that there is no noticeable distinction in the respondents' views regarding the level of parental involvement in the Grade One reading intervention program. Regarding Vocabulary Development, the p-value, which stands above the significance level of 0.05, is 0.108. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When categorized by family size, The analysis suggests that there is no noticeable distinction in the respondents' views regarding the level of parental involvement in the Grade One reading intervention program.

The p-value for Fluency Development was 0.057, over the significance threshold of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When categorized by family size, The analysis suggests that there is no noticeable distinction in the respondents' views regarding the level of parental involvement in the Grade One reading intervention program. The p-value for comprehension

development was 0.078, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When categorized by family size, there is no noticeable distinction in the respondents' views regarding the level of parental involvement in the Grade One reading intervention program.

Table 28. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent’s Assessment when Grouped According to Family Size*

Indicators	Family Size	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Oral Language Development	1 to 2	172.08	10.444	0.064	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	196.80				
	5 to 6	178.61				
	7 to 8	146.70				
	9 to 10	72.00				
	11 to 12	90.88				
Phonological Awareness Development	1 to 2	168.03	9.873	0.079	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	196.66				
	5 to 6	179.39				
	7 to 8	142.73				
	9 to 10	82.25				
	11 to 12	101.00				
Phonics and Word Recognition Development	1 to 2	147.25	9.646	0.086	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	198.07				
	5 to 6	176.62				
	7 to 8	159.43				
	9 to 10	67.25				
	11 to 12	155.50				
Vocabulary Development	1 to 2	151.11	9.017	0.108	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	198.38				
	5 to 6	175.59				
	7 to 8	158.93				
	9 to 10	88.75				
	11 to 12	146.00				
Fluency Development	1 to 2	132.75	10.741	0.057	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	198.88				
	5 to 6	177.31				
	7 to 8	146.60				
	9 to 10	178.25				
	11 to 12	150.25				
Comprehension Development	1 to 2	145.11	9.915	0.078	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	196.24				
	5 to 6	180.25				
	7 to 8	162.17				
	9 to 10	39.00				
	11 to 12	147.00				
Implementation	1 to 2	140.72	9.748	0.083	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	198.96				
	5 to 6	175.63				
	7 to 8	156.37				
	9 to 10	112.50				
	11 to 12	159.50				
Post Implementation	1 to 2	147.47	9.429	0.093	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	199.42				
	5 to 6	172.74				
	7 to 8	165.87				
	9 to 10	100.00				
	11 to 12	168.13				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Likewise, Mante, Awereh & Kumea (2024) posit that family structure affects parental involvement. According to them, the challenge of single parenthood, poverty, family crises, increasing involvement of women in work and national development affects parental involvement in children’s educational endeavors. That is, children with a single parent or stepparents are provided with less support in comparison to children who live in two-parent families. Looking from another dimension, Jordan et al (2021) reiterate further that mothers spend more time dealing with their children’s homework than fathers and that some parents do not see it as their duty since teachers are paid to teach the children.

5. Test of Significant Difference on the Level of Participation in the Program's Stages of Implementation

Table 29. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent's Assessment When Grouped According to Age*

Indicators	Age	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Implementation	20 and below	167.00	1.214	0.270	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	21-30	191.88				
	31-40	186.92				
	41-50	175.37				
	51-60	180.18				
Post-Implementation	61 and above	180.83	3.153	0.076	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	20 and below	172.56				
	21-30	192.87				
	31-40	187.33				
	41-50	169.78				
	51-60	206.27				
	61 and above	132.50				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 29 compares respondent assessments of parent involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One kids when grouped by age using the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test. P-value for implementation was 0.270, over the significance threshold of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by age, there is no noticeable difference in the respondent's view of the parent's level of participation in the reading intervention program for the students in Grade One. And, according to post-Implementation, the significance criterion of 0.05 is not met by the p-value, which is 0.076. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by age, there is no discernible disparity in the respondent's assessment of the level of parental involvement in the reading intervention program for learners in Grade One.

Mudzielwana's (2014) study found the following to be factors hindering parents from helping children develop reading skills: (1) parents who cannot read and write, i.e. no knowledge, (2) parents who work far from home and come home once a month, (3) parents who do not have the time and who say they are not educators, (4) single parent who is too busy hustling or are lazy, (5) parents who find it difficult to help because they do not know where to start, (6) mothers who work night shifts and nanny cannot read, (7) no reading books at home for developing the reading skill, and (8) parents' level of education.

Table 30. *Mann Whitney U – Test: Comparison on the Respondent's Assessment on the Parent's Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Sex*

Indicators	Sex	Mean Rank	U-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Implementation	Female	188.86	8810.5	0.117	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	162.95				
Post-Implementation	Female	188.38	8656.0	0.179	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Male	166.17				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 30 presents the comparison of the respondent's assessment of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One pupils using the Mann Whitney U-Test, grouped by sex. The implementation's p-value was 0.117, exceeding the 0.05 significance level. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, the respondent's assessment of the parent's degree of participation in the reading intervention program for the students in Grade One does not show any variation. Additionally, the post-implementation p-value was 0.179, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When grouped by sex, there is no noticeable difference in the respondent's perception of the parent's involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners.

Similarly, findings suggested that parental involvement significantly influenced children's reading and fluency. This is consistent with the findings of Chowa, Masa, and Tucker (2023) that there is a correlation between at home parental involvement and English examination scores and continuous assessment scores. It also agrees with Senechal and LeFevre (2022) that early home literacy experiences were indirectly related to later reading performances.

Table 31 displays the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison on the respondent's estimate of the parent's level of involvement in the Grade One learners' reading intervention program, organized by occupation. Implementation reports that the p-value was 0.021, less significant than the 0.05 threshold. The null hypothesis was thus disproved. When categorized by occupation, there is a notable discrepancy in the respondents' evaluations of the parents' involvement under the program for reading intervention designed for Grade One learners.

In contrast, the p-value for post-Implementation was higher above the significance level of 0.05 at 0.065. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When categorized by occupation, the respondent's assessment of the parent's level of participation in the

reading intervention program for first graders does not show any variation.

Table 31. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent’s Assessment when Grouped According to Occupation*

Indicators	Occupation	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Implementation	Regular	188.68	11.597	0.021	Reject Ho	Significant
	Probationary	164.70				
	Housewife	185.84				
	None	194.85				
	Others	233.63				
Post Implementation	Regular	191.81	8.853	0.065	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	Probationary	166.57				
	Housewife	180.89				
	None	196.03				
	Others	224.07				

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

There are varied factors which play a role in the level of educational support parents provide their children. There is a remarkable difference in the school-parent relationship across diverse income levels (Matthews, McPherson-Berg, Quinton, Rotunda, & Morote, 2017). Families with low socioeconomic status (SES) participate less in their child’s education when compared to families of a middle and higher SES. It is thought that this may be due to barriers faced by parents including low income, lack of resources, inflexible work schedules, ethnic/racial differences, and transportation issues. These obstacles affect the educational parent involvement in low-income households in significant ways. Families may not have access to resources supporting optimal home environments which provide intellectual and cognitive stimulation including activities to help support activation of the child’s attention span, curiosity, memory, and development of the brain leading to elevated risks for lower achievement of students (Bunijevac & Durisic, 2017; Duncan & Rapp, 2021; Matthews et al., 2017). It is important to note that not only do low-income families have limited access to community cognitive developmental resources but families, not necessarily low income, from small town/rural neighborhoods also have a disadvantage of benefitting from community resources as well (Froiland, 2021).

Table 32 displays the results of the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine the significant variation in parent engagement in Grade One learners’ reading intervention program when the parents are grouped based on their occupation. Regarding Implementation, A significant difference between Probationary and Others was discovered using the post hoc test using Dunn's testing and Bonferroni correction, with a p-value of 0.0006.

Table 32. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent’s Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Occupation*

Occupation	Implementation	
	p-value	Remarks
Regular vs. Probationary	0.0711	Not Significant
Regular vs. Housewife	0.8559	Not Significant
Regular vs. None	0.8048	Not Significant
Regular vs. Others	0.0229	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Housewife	0.1915	Not Significant
Probationary vs. None	0.2337	Not Significant
Probationary vs. Others	0.0006	Significant
Housewife vs. None	0.7351	Not Significant
Housewife vs. Others	0.0284	Not Significant
None vs. Others	0.1847	Not Significant

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Parents with a lower SES are more likely to live in less advantaged neighborhoods. Community institutions such as childcare centers, churches, libraries, and community centers are important resources for building social networks. However, these community institutions vary across different school neighborhoods. Often, neighborhoods with a large number of schools with free and reduced lunch have fewer institutions, not allowing for adequate opportunities for residents to interact with one another in formal settings. The lack of formal settings for residents to interact among one another increases the difficulty of building social networks to help advance child education (Li & Fischer, 2017).

Table 33 displays, when grouped by educational attainment, the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison on the respondent's opinion of the parent's level of participation in the reading intervention program of the Grade One learners. The p-value for implementation was 0.000, which is less significant than the 0.05 level. The null hypothesis was thus rejected. When categorized by educational achievement, there is a substantial difference in the respondent's judgment of the parent's level of participation in the reading intervention program for the Grade One learners.

Table 33. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent’s Assessment When Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

Indicators	Educational Attainment	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Implementation	Elementary	164.86	24.854	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	164.87				
	College	204.33				
	Post-Graduate	230.44				
	Vocational	123.23				
Post-Implementation	Elementary	167.21	17.949	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
	High School	174.77				
	College	200.25				
	Post-Graduate	213.91				
	Vocational	122.08				

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Furthermore, the p-value for post-implementation was 0.001, which is less significant than the 0.05 level. The null hypothesis was thus disproved. When categorized by educational achievement, there is a substantial difference in the respondent's judgment of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program designed for Grade One learners.

Principals play a significant role in creating and implementing a successful school-parent involvement program in the educational setting and must consider ways to promote parent activity in the school community. It is necessary for administration to coordinate, manage, support, fund, or recognize parental involvement for teachers to successfully involve parents. Administration and teachers need to recognize the value of parental involvement and set goals for implementing programs that encourage such involvement in schools (Richardson, 2019).

Table 34. *Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to Determine where the Significant Difference Lie on the Parent’s Level of Participation in the Reading Intervention Program of the Grade One Learners when Grouped According to Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Implementation		Post Implementation	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Elementary vs. High School	0.9997	Not Significant	0.8548	Not Significant
Elementary vs. College	0.3250	Not Significant	0.4179	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Post-Graduate	0.1615	Not Significant	0.3268	Not Significant
Elementary vs. Vocational	0.3375	Not Significant	0.3064	Not Significant
High School vs. College	0.0013	Significant	0.0412	Not Significant
High School vs. Post-Graduate	0.0157	Not Significant	0.0156	Not Significant
High School vs. Vocational	0.0436	Not Significant	0.0120	Not Significant
College vs. Post-Graduate	0.3217	Not Significant	0.6101	Not Significant
College vs. Vocational	0.0000	Significant	0.0000	Significant
Post-Graduate vs. Vocational	0.0006	Significant	0.0037	Significant

Note: "If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 34 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to ascertain the point at which, when grouped by educational achievement, the level of parental involvement in the reading intervention program varies significantly for students in Grade One. Regarding Implementation, there were significant differences between High School and College. The post ad hoc test using Dunn's test with Bonferroni Correction revealed the following: College (p-value = 0.0013), College and Vocational (p-value = 0.0000), and Post-Graduate and Vocational (p-value = 0.0006). Using Dunn's test and Bonferroni correction, the post ad hoc test, in line with post-implementation, revealed significant differences between Post-Graduate and Vocational (p-value = 0.0037) and College and Vocational (p-value = 0.0000).

Oftentimes policy makers, educators, and citizens proclaim parents who struggle with literacy will have low achieving children who have literacy difficulties and that low achieving children who struggle with literacy will have parents with literacy difficulties, thereby creating a cycle of underachievement. Some policy makers, educators, and citizens also claim that students who are at risk for literacy underachievement can be identified based on parental literacy difficulties which is put forward as a cause of the child's illiteracy (Hannon, 2019). Hannon (2019) suggests targeting parents' and children's literacy at the same time in the same program, to break the cycle of underachievement.

Table 35 demonstrates the comparison of the respondent's assessment of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners based on family income using the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test. Regarding Implementation, At 0.221, the p-value exceeded the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One Learners. The p-value for post-Implementation was 0.384, over the significance threshold of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One Learners.

Table 35. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent’s Assessment when Grouped According to Income of a Family*

Indicators	Family Income	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Implementation	15,000 and below	178.89	5.720	0.221	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	185.21				
	30,001 to 45,000	209.41				
	45,001 to 60,000	161.03				
	60,001 and above	222.23				
Post-Implementation	15,000 and below	177.20	4.165	0.384	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	15,001 to 30,000	194.65				
	30,001 to 45,000	193.26				
	45,001 to 60,000	159.87				
	60,001 and above	210.16				

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 35 demonstrates the comparison of the respondent's assessment of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One learners based on family income using the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test. Regarding Implementation, At 0.221, the p-value exceeded the significance level of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One Learners. The p-value for post-Implementation was 0.384, over the significance threshold of 0.05. Thus, it was not possible to reject the null hypothesis. When classifying respondents based on family income, there is no discernible difference in their evaluations of the parents' involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One Learners.

Research has disproved the common misconception that parents of lower socioeconomic status do not want to be involved with their child's school when parents of lower income want to be involved just as much as families from average and higher incomes in decision making and school activities. Impoverished parents have a desire to become more involved with their child's school but factors, as discussed above, hinder them from feeling comfortable participating (Matthews et al., 2017). Teachers need to have knowledge of the misconception that parents of lower SES do not wish to be involved. It is important for teachers to establish effective school-parent relationships in lower income families.

Table 36. *Kruskal – Wallis H – Test: Comparison on the Respondent’s Assessment when Grouped According to Family Size*

Indicators	Family Size	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Implementation	1 to 2	140.72	9.748	0.083	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	3 to 4	198.96				
	5 to 6	175.63				
	7 to 8	156.37				
	9 to 10	112.50				
Post-Implementation	11 to 12	159.50	9.429	0.093	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
	1 to 2	147.47				
	3 to 4	199.42				
	5 to 6	172.74				
	7 to 8	165.87				
	9 to 10	100.00				
	11 to 12	168.13				

Note: “If p value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05) reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho.”

Table 36 shows, when grouped by family size, the Kruskal-Wallis H-Test of the comparison on the respondent's opinion of the parent's level of participation in the reading intervention program of the Grade One learners. In terms of implementation, the p-value was more than significant at the 0.05 level, at 0.083. Thus, the null hypothesis could not be disproved. Sorted according to family size, there is no discernible difference in the respondent's opinion of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One pupils. Furthermore, the post-implementation p-value was 0.093, above the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis could not be disproved. Sorted according to family size, there is no discernible difference in the respondent's opinion of the parent's level of involvement in the reading intervention program for the Grade One pupils.

According to Doyle and Zhang (2021), to improve the educational outcomes of children, intervention programs have become increasingly popular. Family literacy programs can result in positive effects on children's literacy development. However, the recruitment and retention of families continue to be rising issues with these programs. Discoveries from a study conducted by Doyle

and Zhang (2021) identified parents' motivations for participating in family literacy programs, parents' expectations of what the literacy program entails, and parents' reasons for remaining in the program. Results from the study recommend that parents re-program beliefs and expectations must be taken into account for recruitment of families as well as a choice in the program type to help meet family needs and to keep them engaged. Educators and administrators need to take parent recommendations and expectations into account when trying to establish adequate parent-school involvement.

6. Problems Encountered by Parents in Their Participation in the Program

Table 37. *Problems Encountered by Parents*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. There was not enough parents' participation for the reading intervention program of the Grade One pupils by the school. (Walang sapat na pakikilahok ng magulang para sa programang interbensyon sa pagbasa sa mga nasa Unang Baitang ng eskwelahan.)	2.76	Sometimes Encountered
2. Limited instructional materials are present in schools and at home. (Mga limitadong kagamitan at libro sa pag aaral ang ginagamit sa paaralan at tahanan.)	2.92	Sometimes Encountered
3. Parents have no time to tutor their children to read at home. (Walang oras upang turuan ang kanilang mga anak na magbasa ng kanilang mga magulang.)	2.60	Sometimes Encountered
4. The teachers have a tough time handling pupils' disruptive behavior in class which needs parents' authority over their child. (Nahihirapan ang mga guro na pangasiwaan ang hindi magandang gawi ng kanilang estudyante.)	2.68	Sometimes Encountered
5. There are students who are not participating in class or do not participate in reading. (May mga estudyanteng hindi nakikilahok sa klase o sa pagbasa.)	2.78	Sometimes Encountered
6. The teaching methodology of the teacher is as old as his/her strategies or method of instruction as used inside the class which needs parents' participation. (Ang pamamaraan ng pagtuturo ng guro ay hindi na angkop sa klase.)	2.36	Barely Encountered
7. The parents do not give time and effort in training their child at home particularly reading. (Hindi nagbibigay ng oras at pagsisikap na sanayin ang kanilang anak sa bahay sa pagbasa.)	2.44	Barely Encountered
8. The parents have no devoted time in making their child excel in school. (Walang oras ang mga magulang para turuan maging mahusay ang kanilang anak.)	2.42	Barely Encountered
9. There is no harmonious relationship between the teacher and parents in making the learner perform in school. (Walang magandang relasyon sa pagitan ng guro at magulang para maging maahusay ang mag-aaral.)	2.31	Barely Encountered
10. The learner is always late and loiter inside the school which needs disciplinary actions of their parents. (Ang mag-aaral ay lagging huli at nag-uuli lamang sa paaralan.)	2.26	Barely Encountered
Grand Mean	2.55	Sometimes Encountered

Legend: "Not Encountered (1.00 – 1.50)", "Barely Encountered (1.51 – 2.50)", "Sometimes Encountered (2.51 – 3.50)", "Often Encountered (3.51 – 4.50)", "Always Encountered (4.51 – 5.00)"

Table 37 shows the respondent's assessment on the problems met in the parent's participation in the reading intervention program of Grade One learners. The grand mean was 2.55 with a verbal interpretation of "Sometimes Encountered." This implied that the respondents sometimes encountered the problems met in the parent's participation in the reading intervention program of Grade One learners.

The highest indicator, "Obsolete instructional materials are present in the schools and at home" got a mean of 2.92. This revealed that the respondents need to buy updated materials for reading. According to the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) Act of 2001 (U.S. Department of Education), parents play a significant role in promoting their children's academic achievement. Regardless of the legislation, schools should and are encouraged to increase their efforts in developing innovative ways to involve parents in their children's academic growth. According to Lai and Vadeboncoeur (2012), a school's role to foster parental involvement has evolved into passive behavior rather than a genuine effort. Furthermore, when attempting to assign responsibility for student accomplishment, parents are frequently used as scapegoats. To illustrate, some educators hold parents accountable for their children's academic shortcomings (e.g., "Parents just don't care about school" or "If only the parents helped at home"). Despite these observations, research continues to support parental participation as an effective approach to boost academic attainment. According to research, parents are a significant independent variable in inspiring their children to learn (Williams & Holbein, 2015).

The above results imply that there is a need for updated instructional materials in both schools and homes, suggesting that respondents recognize the importance of acquiring current resources for reading. Despite the No Child Left Behind (NCLB) Act emphasizing parental involvement in promoting academic achievement, schools often exhibit passive behavior in fostering such engagement, and parents are sometimes unfairly blamed for students' academic shortcomings. However, research consistently supports parental participation as a crucial factor in enhancing academic success, highlighting parents' significant role in inspiring their children to learn (Williams & Holbein, 2015).

The second indicator elicited that "there are students who are not participating in class or does not participate in reading" with a mean of 2.78. This showed that there are learners who are not active in class discussions. This needs good parental involvement so that the teacher can report to the parents what their child does in school. Numerous school constructs, including engagement, are correlated

with parental involvement. Examples of parental involvement include attending parent-teacher conferences, taking part in extracurricular activities, keeping an eye on student grades, instilling parental values, helping with homework, and offering both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Nonetheless, Lai and Vadeboncoeur (2012) discovered that parents have not been sufficiently involved in schooling.

On the third rank was the statement saying that “There is not enough parents’ participation for the reading intervention program of the Grade One pupils by the school” with a mean of 2.76. This indicated that the parent’s participation is not enough for the reading intervention program. On the contrary, this requires active parental involvement to improve students' academic performance. Despite differences in definitions, educators concur that parental support is essential for students' academic performance. Parental participation is traditionally defined like helping with homework, volunteering, interacting with teachers, visiting open houses, back-to-school nights, and parent-teacher conferences, among other activities both at school and at home (Epstein et al., 2019). Parental participation is defined by Lopez, Scribner, and Mahitivanichcha (2011) as "supporting student academic achievement or participating in school-initiated functions."

The lowest indicator showed that “The learner is always late and loiter inside the school which needs disciplinary actions of their parents” with a mean of 2.26. This elucidated that the learners may loiter in the school. This is part of parental involvement to mitigate this kind of situation. Epstein et al.'s (2019) paradigm includes six categories ensure the child's health and safety through healthy home environments that support behavior and learning, as well as through parenting, child rearing, continual supervision, discipline, and direction at every age. Communicating with the school regarding academic achievement through memos, notices, report cards, and conferences is the primary duty of schools (Type 2). Parental involvement in school activities (e.g., events, workshops, or programs for their own educational development) is the fundamental responsibility of schools (Type 3). Schools' primary duty (Type 4) is to inform parents on how to start, oversee, and support their children with their schoolwork or other learning activities. Parent participation in committees that monitor academic progress is a fundamental responsibility of schools (Type 5). Collaborating with the community is a crucial part of schools' fundamental function (Type 6), and this includes incorporating a variety of community agencies and resources to assist school activities (Epstein, Coates, Salinas, Sanders, and Simon, 2017).

The result suggests that some learners consistently arrive late and linger within the school premises, indicating a need for parental intervention to address disciplinary issues. Epstein et al.'s paradigm outlines various responsibilities for both parents and schools to ensure a conducive learning environment and promote academic success. Parents are responsible for creating a healthy home environment, providing continual supervision, discipline, and direction to their children. Additionally, they should communicate with the school regarding academic progress and participate in school activities and committees aimed at monitoring academic progress. On the other hand, schools are responsible for informing parents about supporting their children's learning, involving parents in school activities, and collaborating with the community to enhance educational opportunities. This implies that addressing tardiness and disciplinary issues among learners requires a collaborative effort between parents and schools, as outlined in Epstein et al.'s framework for effective parental involvement in education.

Conclusion

Based on the findings derived, the following conclusions were drawn: Majority of the respondents comprised of those 31-40 years of age, female dominated, were in their Regular Positions in their job, College graduates, were earning 15,000 and below, has family members of 3 to 4, and were engaged in the PTA.

The research discovered that parents exhibited significant engagement in fostering their children's reading skills development. This indicates that parents acknowledged the importance of nurturing their children's reading abilities.

The parents actively took part in the various stages of the program's implementation. During this phase, it was observed that the respondents instructed their children on how to engage and collaborate in classroom activities. This indicates that the parents have complete faith in the program's implementation.

When grouped by profile, there is no significant difference in the respondent's assessment of the parent's level of participation in their children's reading abilities development, except for occupation and educational attainment which have a significant difference in the respondent's assessment. Hence, this can be attributed to the fact that parents are busy, or they may consider themselves less competent without formal education.

When grouped by profile, there is no significant difference in the respondent's assessment of the parent's level of participation in the program's stages of implementation, except for occupation and educational attainment, which have a significant difference in the respondent's assessment. Likewise, this can be attributed to the fact that parents are busy, or they may consider themselves less competent without formal education.

The research findings revealed that respondents occasionally faced challenges regarding parental involvement in the reading intervention program for Grade One students. It was noted that the lack of instructional materials and access to reading resources could impact parental participation. Consequently, parents depend on having adequate instructional materials to effectively implement the intervention program.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following were recommended: Schools may collaborate with parents in the reinforcement activities focusing on the development of the reading skills of their children. They may volunteer to participate as reading development partners.

Properly monitor and evaluate the implementation of the program to sustain the high participation of the parents. Make it a point that feedback is cascaded to them as well.

Parents must be oriented further on their integral part in the development of reading skills of the children. Schools must provide training and lectures to make the parents more able in the conduct of home-based reading reinforcement activities.

Parents must be consulted in the implementation of the program. Likewise, schools must solicit best practices to make the parents more able to participate in the reading intervention program.

Parents should cooperate with the school to address the problem on inadequacy or in the availability of materials by either assisting in the production of improvised instructional materials or outsourcing innovative learning materials through the PTA contribution.

Further research is also recommended using upgraded intervention programs coming from the monitoring and evaluation of the existing program while utilizing different scope of population and location.

References

- Acabado, C. (2018). Impact of parental involvement on reading development of learners. Research Gate DOI: 10.13140/RG2.2.35995.31524
- Akey, K. (2017). The adolescent's sense of being literate: Reshaping through classroom transitions (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Oklahoma).
- Allen-DeBoer, R., Malmgren, K. W., & Glass, M. (2016). Reading instruction for youth with emotional and behavioral disorders in a juvenile correctional facility. *Behavioral Disorders*, 32(1), 18–28
- Ash, G. E. (2015). What did Abigail mean? *Educational Leadership*, 62(5), 48–53.
- Ayoubian, A., Nasiripour, A. A., Tabibi, S. J., & Bahadori, M. (2020). Evaluation of Facilitators and Barriers to Implementing Evidence-Based Practice in the Health Services: A Systematic Review. *Galen medical journal*, 9, e1645. <https://doi.org/10.31661/gmj.v9i0.1645>
- Barcena, A. T. (2012). The non formal education program in sto. domingo and magsingal districts, division of ilocos sur. Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City.
- Barth A. E., Barnes M., Francis D., Vaughn S., York M. (2015). Inferential processing among adequate and struggling adolescent comprehenders and relations to reading comprehension. *Reading and Writing: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 28, 587-609.
- Barton, A. C, Drake, C, Perez, J. G., St. Louis, K., & George, M. (2014). Ecologies of parental engagement in urban education. *Educational Researcher*, 33(4), 3-12.
- Boulay, B., Goodson, B., Frye, M., Blocklin, M., & Price, C. (2015). Summary of research generated by striving readers on the effectiveness of interventions for struggling adolescent readers. NCEE 2016-4001. Jessup, MD: National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance.
- Bradley, F. C. (2020). The impact of parental involvement on the reading achievement of fourth grade African American Males in the Tidewater Region of Virginia.
- Brodin, J., & Renblad, K. (2019). Improvement of preschool children's speech and language skills. *Early Child Development and Care*, 190(14), 2205-2213. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004430.2018.1564917>.
- Brown, S. L., Manning, W. D., & Stykes, J. B. (2015). Family Structure and Child Well-Being: Integrating Family Complexity. *Journal of marriage and the family*, 77(1), 177–190. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.1214>
- Carino, M. & Marcos, M.G. (2013). The non-formal education program of Dolores, Lagangilag, San Juan, and Tayum districts, division of Abra. Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City.
- Castro, M., Expósito-Casas, E., López-Martín, E., Lizasoain, L., Navarro-Asencio, E. and Gaviria, J.L. (2015). Parental involvement on student academic achievement: A meta-analysis, *Educational Research Review*, Volume 14, Pages 33-46, ISSN 1747-938X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.01.002>
- Cheng, A. W. Y., & Lai, C. Y. Y. (2023). Parental stress in families of children with special educational needs: a systematic review. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 14, 1198302. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2023.1198302>
- Cheong, J. W. (2013). University extension program and their impact. The Cases of UPCA. Unpublished Doctor's Dissertation, University of the Philippines, Los Baños, Lagun
- Clark, M. K., & Kamhi, A. G. (2014). Influence of prior knowledge and interest on fourth-and fifth-grade passage comprehension on the qualitative reading inventory-4. *Language, Speech & Hearing Services in Schools*, 45(4), 291–301.

- Contaio, M. R. (2013). The effectiveness of the extension program of UNP. Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City.
- Corpuz, B. (2014). Pupils reading comprehension level and their performance in English, Science and Math: A basis for proposed strategic intervention plan. Unpublished Dissertation, St. Paul University Philippines.
- Coutland, M. C., & Leslie, L. (2020). Beliefs and practices of three literacy instructors in elementary teacher education. *Alberta Journal of Educational Research*, 56(1), 19–30.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2020). *The flat world and education: How America's commitment to equity will determine our future*. New York, NY: Teacher's College, Columbia University. ISBN: 978-0807749621
- Davis-Kean, P., Tighe, L. and Waters, N. (2020). The role of parent educational attainment in parenting and children's development. DOI: 10.31234/osf.io/ndmxb
- Denton, C. A., Fletcher, J. M., Anthony, J. L., & Francis, D. J. (2016). An evaluation of intensive intervention for students with persistent reading difficulties. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 39(5), 447–466.
- Department of Education. (2015). Utilization of the early grade reading assessment (EGRA) and early grade math assessment (EGMA) tools for system assessment (DO 57, s. 2015). Retrieved from http://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/DO_s2015_57.pdf.
- Deysolong, JA (2023). The critical role of parent involvement in the learning process of students, Research Gate, DOI: 10.6084/m9.figshare.22999787
- Diaz-Iso, A., Velasco, E.' and Meza, P. (2022). Interventions to improve reading competence: a systematic review, Research Gate Revista de Educacion, 398. October-December 2022, pp. 237-267.
- Diem, K. (2011). Using research methods to evaluate your extension program educational design Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey.
- Dulay, KM, Law, SY, McBride, C., and Suk-Han Ho, C. (2021). Reciprocal effects of morphological awareness, vocabulary knowledge, and word reading: A cross-lagged panel analysis in Chinese, *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, Volume 206, 105100, ISSN 0022-0965, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2021.105100>
- Ehri, LC (2014) Orthographic mapping in the acquisition of sight word reading, spelling memory, and vocabulary learning, *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 18:1, 5-21, DOI: 10.1080/10888438.2013.81935
- Elleman, AM (2019). Reading comprehension research: implications for practice and policy, *Sage Journals*, Volume 6, Issue 1, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6686-589X> <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732218816339>
- Eneriz-Wiemer, M., Sanders, L.M., Barr, D.A. and Mendoza, F.S. MD, (2014). Parental limited English proficiency and health outcomes for children with special health care needs: a systematic review. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2013.10.003>
- Faggella-Luby, M., Schumaker, J. S., & Deshler, D. D. (2017). Embedded learning strategy instruction: Story-structure pedagogy in heterogeneous secondary literature classes. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 30(2), 131–147.
- Fan, X., & Chen, M.J. (2001). Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: a meta-analysis. *Educational Psychology Review*, 13, 1-22.
- Fatimayin, F.F. (2020). Impact of parental involvement in helping children develop reading skills, Research Gate, 19(1):95-112
- Feldman H. M. (2019). How young children learn language and speech. *Pediatrics in Review*, 40(8), 398–411. <https://doi.org/10.1542/pir.2017-0325>
- Fernandez, R. (2016). Phonemic awareness: A prerequisite in learning to read. *Modern Teacher*, 55 (6).
- Flynn, L. J., Zheng, X., & Swanson, L. H. (2012). Instructing struggling older readers: A selective meta-analysis of intervention research. *Learning Disabilities Research & Practice*, 27(1), 21–32
- Garces-Bacsal, R.M. (2020). Diverse books for diverse children: Building an early childhood diverse book list for social and emotional learning, *Journal of Childhood Literacy*, Volume 22, Issue 1, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468798420901856>
- Garcia, A.S. and de Guzman, M.T. (2020). The meanings and ways of parental involvement among low-income Filipinos, *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, Volume 53, Pages 343-354, ISSN 0885-2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2020.05.013>.
- Geske, A. and Ozola, A. (2020). Parents' impact on students' reading achievement. 3:656 DOI:1017770/sie2020vol3.5049
- Golubović, Š., Đorđević, M., Ilić, S., & Nikolašević, Ž. (2022). Engagement of preschool-aged children in daily routines. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(22), 14741. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192214741>
- Hancock, J. W. (2012). The effect of reciprocal teaching plus across three content areas on reading comprehension in seventh and eighth grade students (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- Henderson, M., Ryan, T., Boud, D., Dawson, P., Phillips, M., Molloy, E., & Mahoney, P. (2021). The usefulness of feedback. *Active*

Learning in Higher Education, 22(3), 229-243. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787419872393>

Hillier, K. (2024). How having conversations with children builds their language — and strengthens family connections. Retrieved from <https://theconversation.com/>

Hustedde, C. and Satish, V. (2016). Extension education evaluation: An evolutionary perspective with implications for theory and practice. paper presentation, Extension Education Evaluation Topical Interest Group American Evaluation Association Annual Meeting, Atlanta, Georgia, November 6- 9, 1996.

Hwang, J. K., Lawrence, J. F., Mo, E., Snow, C. E. (2015). Differential effects of a systematic vocabulary intervention on adolescent language minority students with varying levels of English proficiency. *International Journal of Bilingualism*, 19(3), 314–332

Jiménez, R. T., Smith, P. H., & Teague, B. L. (2019). Transnational and community literacies for teachers. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 53(1), 16–26.

Johnson, K. (2023). What is phonological awareness? Retrieved from <https://www.understood.org/en/articles/> March 29, 2024

Jones, N. M. (2014). The role of personality and professional learning community quality in predicting teacher effectiveness (Doctoral dissertation, George Mason University).

Joshi, M. R., Dahlgren, M., & Boulware-Gooden, R. (2012). Teaching reading in an inner-city school through a multi-sensory teaching approach. *Annals of Dyslexia*, 52, 229–242.

Kakotree (2023). The role of parents in supporting phonics learning, Retrieved from <https://kokotree.com/> March 29, 2024

Kaminski, R. A., Powell-Smith, K., Hommel, A., McMahan, R., & Aguayo, K. B. (2014). Development of a tier 3 curriculum to teach early literacy skills. *Journal of Early Intervention*, 36(4), 313–332.

Kelly, N.E. (2020). Family engagement in schools: Parent, educator, and community perspectives, <https://journals.sagepub.com/> <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020973024>

Kibler, A. (2019). Talking writing: Adolescent English learners in the content areas (Doctoral dissertation, Stanford University).

Kim, K., Birditt, K., Zarit, S., and Fingerman, K. (2019). Typology of parent-child ties within families: Associations with psychological well-being. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 34(4):448-458 DOI:10.1037/fam0000595

King, S. A., Lemons, C. J., & Hill, D. R. (2012). Response to intervention in secondary schools: Considerations for administrators. *National Association of Secondary School Principals. NASSP Bulletin*, 96(1), 5–22.

Kirsch, C., & Bergeron-Morin, L. (2023). Educators, parents and children engaging in literacy activities in multiple languages: an exploratory study. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 20(4), 1386–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2023.2195658>

Ko, T., & Hughes, M. T. (2015). Reading comprehension instruction for adolescents with learning disabilities: A reality check. *Education Sciences*, 5(4), 413–439.

Lanford, J.E. (2021). The importance of fathers for child development, *Psychology Today*, <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/>

Lareau, A. (2017). Social class differences in family-school relationship: The importance of cultural capital. *Sociology of Education*, 60, 73-85.

Lareau, A. (2013). *Unequal childhoods: Class, race, and family life*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Lareau, A., & Shumar, W. (2016). The problem of individualism in family-school policies. *Sociology of Education*, 69, 24-39.

Law, J., Levickis, P., McKean, C., Nolan, C. and Goldfeld, S. (2017). *Oral language as a foundation for learning*. Melbourne: Murdoch Children’s Research Institute. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>

Lee, N. (2023). Fostering positive parent-child relationships: Communication strategies. <https://thearkgroup.org/>

LeVos, JS (2021). What is phonological awareness? A guide for parents. Retrieved from <https://www.beginlearning.com/parent-resources/> March 29, 2024

Li, J., Peng, P., Ma, X. et al. (2023). How does family socioeconomic status influence children’s reading ability? Evidence from Meta-analytic Structural Equation Modeling. *Educ Psychol Rev* 35, 119 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-023-09834-1>

Llego, M. A. (2022). The importance of parental involvement in education. *TeacherPH*. Retrieved September 4, 2022 from, <https://www.teacherph.com/parental-involvement-education>

Macy, M. G., & Bricker, D. D. (2016). Practical applications for using curriculum-based assessment to create embedded learning opportunities for young children. *Young Exceptional Children*, 9(4), 12–21.

Maeng, J., & Lee, J. (2021). Exploring parental involvement and its effects on children's literacy outcomes during COVID-19: A mixed-methods study

Maynard, B. R., Solis, M., Miller, V., & Brendel, K. E. (2017). Mindfulness-based interventions for improving cognition, academic achievement, behavior, and socio-emotional functioning of primary and secondary students. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 13.

Retrieved from https://campbellcollaboration.org/media/k2/attachments/Campbell_systematic_review_-_Mindfulness_and_school_students.pdf

McGeown, S. and Smith, K.C. (2023). Reading engagement matters! a new scale to measure and support children's engagement with books, *The Reading Teacher*, Volume 77, Issue 4, Pages 462-472. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.2267>

Melby-Lervåg, M., Lyster, S. A., & Hulme, C. (2012). Phonological skills and their role in learning to read: a meta-analytic review. *Psychological bulletin*, 138(2), 322–352. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0026744>

Metz, A., Naom, S. F., Halle, T., & Bartley L. (2015). An integrated stage-based framework for implementation of early childhood programs and systems. OPRE Research Brief OPRE 2015 48. Washington, DC: Office of Planning, Research and Evaluation, Administration for Children and Families, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services.

Naparan, G. and Olivar, M.J. (2023). Parental involvement and academic performance of students in online class learning modality. *Research Gate*. Volume 10, Issue 2. DOI: 10.23918/ijsses.v10i1p16.

Newark, DE. (2019). Phonological awareness in early childhood literacy development [Position statement and research brief]. International Literacy Association

Noviant, R. and Suarman, S. (2023). Parenting in cultural perspective: A systematic review of paternal role across cultures, *Research Gate*, 10(1):22-44 DOI:10.29333/ejecs/128

Okorn, A., Verhoeven, M., & Van Baar, A. (2022). The Importance of Mothers' and Fathers' Positive Parenting for Toddlers' and Preschoolers' Social-Emotional Adjustment. *Parenting*, 22(2), 128–151.

Padeliadu, S. and Giazitzidou, S. (2018). A synthesis of research on reading fluency development: Study of eight meta-analysis, *Research Gate* <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>

Parker, C. A., Holland, G., & Jones, D. (2013). The effectiveness of two reading intervention programs in a South Texas urban school district. *National Forum of Applied Educational Research*, 26(3), 1–10.

Parker, D. C. (2012). Examining the potential use of instructionally relevant assessment data in early writing (Doctoral dissertation, University of Minnesota).

Paterson, P. & Elliott, L. N. (2016). Struggling reader to struggling reader: High school students' responses to a cross-age tutoring program. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 49(5), 378–389

Pennock, S. (2023). Effective communication with children: nurturing strong bonds and understanding, Retrieved from <https://quenza.com/blog/knowledge-base/effective-communication-with-children>

Peregoy, S. F., & Boyle, O. F. (2020). English learners reading English: What we know, what we need to know. *Theory into Practice*, 4(2), 237–247.

Pocan, JM, Bailon, L.L., and Pocan, J.P. (2022). Strategic reading intervention for left behind learners in the Philippines, *LLT Journal*, e-SUN 2579-9533, p-ISSN 1410-7201, Vol. 25, No. 2, pp. 367-378

Quan-Hoang, V., Viet-Phuong, L, T. Nguyen, T.H., Minh-Hoang, N., Vuong, T.T., Ha-My Vuong, Manh-Toan, H. (2021). Impacts of parents and reading promotion on creating a reading culture: Evidence from a developing context, *Children and Youth Services Review*, Volume 131,

Raja, G.P., Gangwar, R.P., Rastogi, E. & Bajaj, R. (2023). The role of parental involvement in education-A study. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>

Reed, J. M., Marchand-Martella, N., Martella, R. C., & Kolts, R. L. (2017). Assessing the effects of the reading success level A program with fourth-grade students at a Title I elementary school. *Education & Treatment of Children*, 30(1), 45–68

Reggin, L., Pexman, P., Madigan, S., and Graham, S. (2019). Parents play a key role on fostering children's love of reading. Retrieved from <https://theconversation.com/> on March 29, 2024

Ritchey, K. D., & Goeke, J. L. (2016). Orton-Gillingham and Orton-Gillingham- based reading instruction: A review of the literature PRO-ED, 8700 Shoal Creek Boulevard, Austin, TX 78757-6897. Retrieved from <http://cupdx.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://search-proquestcom.cupdx.idm.oclc.org/docview/62027293?accountid=10248>

Ritchey, K. D., Palombo, K., Silverman, R. D., & Speece, D. L. (2017). Effects of an informational text reading comprehension intervention for fifth-grade students. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 40(2), 68–80

Rollè, L., Gullotta, G., Trombetta, T., Curti, L., Gerino, E., Brustia, P., & Caldarera, A. M. (2019). Father Involvement and Cognitive Development in Early and Middle Childhood: A Systematic Review. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 2405. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02405>

Santillan, J.P. (2023). Exploring challenges and factors in students' literacy: basis for intervention program development, *Journal of Educational and Management Studies*, Volume 12, Issue 2:14-22; DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.54203/jems.2023.2>

- Schmid, E., & Garrels, V. (2021). Parental involvement and educational success among vulnerable students in vocational education and training. *Educational Research*, 63(4), 456–473. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2021.1988672>
- Servais, K., Derrington, M. L., & Sanders, K. (2019). Professional learning communities: Concepts in action in a principal preparation program, an elementary school team, a leadership team, and a business partnership. *International Journal of Educational Leadership Preparation*, 4(2), 1–11.
- Shahaeian, A., Wang, C., Tucker-Drob, E., Geiger, V., Bus, A. G., & Harrison, L. J. (2018). Early Shared Reading, Socioeconomic Status, and Children's Cognitive and School Competencies: Six Years of Longitudinal Evidence. *Scientific studies of reading: the official journal of the Society for the Scientific Study of Reading*, 22(6), 485–502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2018.1482901>
- Shamsikhani, S., Ahmadi, F., Kazemnejad, A., & Vaismoradi, M. (2022). Meaning of Respect for Older People in Family Relationships. *Geriatrics (Basel, Switzerland)*, 7(3), 57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geriatrics7030057>
- Shen, S., Doyle-Thomas, K. A. R., Beesley, L., Karmali, A., Williams, L., Tanel, N., & McPherson, A. C. (2017). How and why should we engage parents as co-researchers in health research? A scoping review of current practices. *Health expectations an international journal of public participation in health care and health policy*, 20(4), 543–554. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12490>
- Steiner, L.M., Hindin, A. & Rizzuto, K.C. (2022). Developing children's literacy learning through skillful parent–child shared book readings. *Early Childhood Educ J* 50, 539–553 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-021-01170-9>
- Teepe, RX, Molenaar, I, Oostdam, r., Fukkink, R and Verhoeven, L. (2019). Helping parents enhance vocabulary development in preschool children: Effects of a family literacy program, *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, Volume 48, Pages 226-236, ISSN 0885-2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2019.03.001>.
- Tekyi-Arhin, O. (2023). Strategies for promoting literacy development in young children for teachers and parents, *Research Gate* <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369022078> DOI:1013140/RG.2.2.32720.38407
- Thompson, L. (2023). The importance of student engagement: why active participation is essential for learning, <https://eduengagement.com/>
- Tinapay, A., Seno, R., Fernandez, D.S., and Tirol, S.L., (2021). Exploring student reading comprehension and parental intervention: a literature review, *Research Gate*, Volume 2, Issue 4, 189-199. DOI:10.544.76/iinarj220
- Tolentin, C. (2023). Implementation and challenges of reading intervention programs in face-to-face, *Psychology And Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal 2023* Volume: 14 Pages: 153-168 Document ID: 2023PEMJ1246 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8402809
- Tovani, C. (2014). *Do I really have to teach reading? Content comprehension, grades 6-12?* Portland, ME: Stenhouse Publishers
- Villiger, C. (2020). Benefits and constraints of parent involvement in children's reading promotion: general research trends and evidence from a swiss paired reading intervention study, *Research Gate*, DOI:10.5772/intechopen.93136.
- Waltz, T. J., Powell, B. J., Fernández, M. E., Abadie, B., & Damschroder, L. J. (2019). Choosing implementation strategies to address contextual barriers: diversity in recommendations and future directions. *Implementation science : IS*, 14(1), 42. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-019-0892-4>
- Wang, I.Y., Cheung, R.Y.M. (2023). Parents' gender role attitudes and child adjustment: the mediating role of parental involvement. *Sex Roles* 89, 425–441 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-023-01386-6>
- Yang, L., Chiu, M. M., & Yan, Z. (2021). The power of teacher feedback in affecting student learning and achievement: insights from students' perspective. *Educational Psychology*, 41(7), 821–824. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2021.1964855>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Venuz E. Ogalisco

Polytechnic University of the Philippines - Philippines